

HERPHAESTUS

Heritage in Europe: new technologies in craft for
preserving and innovating futures

Project No. 101095123

Deliverable 4.1

A report on the perceived educational gaps among craft- makers

Funded by
the European Union

Document Control Page	
Project acronym	HEPHAESTUS
Project title	Heritage in EuroPe: new techNologies in crAft for prEServing and innovaTing fUtureS
Action	HORIZON EUROPE Culture, Creativity and Inclusive society
Duration	48 months
Grant no.	101095123
Work package	WP4 – Innovative training curricula for tradition craft-makers of the future
Deliverable	A report on the perceived educational gaps among craft-makers
Tasks	Task n. 4.1.
Starting Date	01/04/2023
Due Date	31/03/2024
Submission Date	31/03/2024
Document type	Deliverable (D4.1)
Version	1
Dissemination level	Public
Abstract	The Report describes the analysis of craft-makers perceived educational gaps. We propose a new framework categorizing skills into five macro-categories. Insights from interviews, an online questionnaire, and a co-creation workshop revealed craft-makers' need for communication and business skills, suggesting avenues for targeted services and educational programs.
Keywords	Skills, resources, competencies, education, training, craft-makers
Statement of originality	This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both.
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Document History

Version	Date	Authors, reviewers, contributors	Changes
D4.1 v1	18/03/2024	Luca Pareschi, Francesca Leonardi (UNITOV)	First full document
D4.1 v1.1	21/03/2024	Alberta Menegaldo (FLV); Elena Raviola (UGOT)	Revised draft by Partners
D4.1 v1.2	28/03/2024	Luca Pareschi, Francesca Leonardi (UNITOV)	Final version

Scheduled updates

Even if not bounded by the GA, we plan to keep collecting data as we develop and test the education and training methodology, so to maintain a virtuous cross fertilisation between data collection, data analysis, and application of results. Therefore we plan to update this deliverable twice, at months 24 and 48.

Version	Expected by project month (M)
RV1	M24
RV2	M48

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ABOUT HEPHAESTUS

Working across the **regional craft ecosystems** of **Bassano del Grappa (IT)**, **Bornholm (DK)**, **Dals Långed (SE)**, and **Venice (IT)**, the overarching ambition of HEPHAESTUS is *to bring together cutting-edge technologies with traditional craft to co-create solutions in the form of a suite of tools, methodologies, and business models to make the future of European craft ecosystems socially, culturally, environmentally, and economically sustainable*. HEPHAESTUS will **test and evaluate solutions** co-created across the four regional craft ecosystems within a **“Future of Craft” Green Living Lab** situated in Bornholm, a Danish Island and regional municipality given the title of World Craft Region. Ultimately, the project sets out to create a **sustainable network** (especially including regional realities) of heritage sites, cultural and creative sectors, institutions, universities, local, regional and national authorities, enterprises, and other relevant stakeholders engaged in preservation of craft heritage that will take the project’s results, further adapt and deploy them in a broader range of craft ecosystems, and ensure a long-lasting legacy of the HEPHAESTUS project. The work of HEPHAESTUS is organized around six work packages, each responsible for one specific objective related to the overarching ambition, namely:

Objective 1: Develop new **sustainable business models** for the craft sectors.

Objective 2: Combine **cutting-edge technologies** with craft materials and processes to research and develop new applications and solutions for the digitisation and innovation of the craft sector to improve sustainability and social innovation.

Objective 3: Explore visions for the role of **craft in the future**, integrating emerging technologies and contributing to the circular economy, by engaging craft communities in a participatory ideation process.

Objective 4: Develop a **lifelong learning methodology** and a set of innovative curricula to equip craft-makers with diverse skillsets for innovation.

Objective 5: Establish a **Green Living Lab** for testing the HEPHAESTUS innovations.

Objective 6: To design and operationalise a **bespoke dissemination, communication, and exploitation** strategy.

To achieve these objectives, the consortium includes prominent universities, business schools and a private organization selected for their proven knowledge and expertise on craft heritage, craft materials, and the use of digital technologies and cutting-edge technologies in craft, the proposed innovative and original contributions as well as their trustworthiness. A unique value added brought to the consortium is represented also by the group of third parties, including craft makers and craft associations, as well as Museums and Municipality representatives, from each of the four regional ecosystems.

Table 1- Hephaestus contacts

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1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Starting at the beginning of the Hephaestus Project, we analysed craft-makers' perceived educational gaps across ecosystems in Bassano del Grappa and Venice, Italy; Bornholm, Denmark; and Dals Långed, Sweden. Aiming to identify relevant skills for craft careers and methods for acquiring these skills, the project's findings will guide further work in Work Package 4. Initial research included a theoretical review of craft skills literature and similar European projects, leading to a new framework categorizing craft skills into five macro-categories. Interviews in Italy and Sweden provided deep insights into craft skills and careers, while an online questionnaire targeted European craft-makers. Efforts to disseminate the questionnaire included collaboration with Hephaestus partners, local craft associations, and networks from other craft-focused European projects, carefully balancing engagement with the need to maintain positive relationships between universities, mediators, and craft-makers. The report will be updated twice to include ongoing questionnaire results. A co-creation workshop in March 2024 in Dals Långed with local craft ambassadors offered a platform to share and validate preliminary findings with craft-makers, focusing on education, skills, and the profession's future. Craft-makers acknowledge the lack in business, communication, and sales skills, vital for their success, and express a preference for outsourcing areas like accounting, legal advice, and digital marketing. This scenario presents opportunities for business and communication specialists to offer tailored services and for educational institutions to develop courses addressing these gaps, enhancing craft-makers' professional development.

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Acknowledgement

HEPHAESTUS project ID 101095123 is funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

2. INTRODUCTION

In this deliverable we describe the results we collected from July 2023 to March 2024 on the perceived educational gaps of craft-makers in the four ecosystems targeted by the Hephaestus Project: Bassano del Grappa (Italy) Venice (Italy), Bornholm (Denmark), Dals Långed (Sweden).

Coherently with the Grant Agreement, the aim of this report is to map perceived educational gaps in craft education, identify which skills are relevant for the craft career, and how to implement the learning or acquisition of those missing skills for craft-makers in different career stages. These results will inform the next tasks within the Work Package 4.

The research started with a Theoretical Review (Section 3) of most relevant academic literature on craft skills and a review of similar European projects on craft and education, understanding their outputs, research, and approaches. Starting from this preliminary review and from the interviews done in the Italian ecosystem, we developed a new theoretical framework which describes and divides craft skills into five macro-categories (Section 4).

We here present the results of the analysis of the interviews (Section 5) done in Bassano del Grappa, Venice and Dals Långed, concerning craft skills and careers, and the results of the questionnaire that we disseminated online to European craft-makers (Section 6). The engagement through interviews with craft-makers was deep and provided enriching results, while they did seem not eager to answer the questionnaire. To overcome this issue, we relied, on the dissemination of the questionnaire, in the efforts provided by Hephaestus partners, by ambassadors, and local associations of craft-makers (i.e. CNA and Confartigianato). Also, we relied on the networks of other craft-focused European projects to disseminate the questionnaire to relevant craft-makers. As requested by project partners, in disseminating the questionnaire we had to balance the need to engage as many craft-makers as possible, with the need to avoid spoiling the relationship between universities and mediators with craft-makers, thus avoiding overwhelming artisans with direct and repeated communications. In any case, we decided to update this report twice during the duration of the project, to update the results of the questionnaire, which will remain open for new answers.

Also, we present the results of the co-creation workshop in Dals Långed (7-8 March 2024) in which Tor Vergata University, Goteborg University, Copenhagen Business School and local craft ambassadors participated (Section 7). It was a generative moment during which we shared the preliminary results of the questionnaire, to validate it with the craft-makers, which discussed relevant themes concerning their education, skills, and ideas of craft as a profession.

A discussion of the results of the analysis of the interviews, of the results of the questionnaire and of the co-creation workshop (Section 8) precedes the conclusions (Section 9).

Craft-makers are aware of their lack of skills in business, communication, and selling skills, crucial for their work's success. While they are keen to learn new crafting techniques independently, they would prefer outsourcing these skills, like accounting, financial management, and digital communication. This opens avenues for specialists in communication and business to create targeted services or consultancies. Educational institutions can also play a role by introducing courses on marketing, photography, and social media management, tailored for craft-makers.

3. THEORETICAL REVIEW

Reviewing the **academic literature** on the relevant skills of craft makers, generally emerges a long list of different types of skills, with some authors focusing also on the resources needed in addition to competencies (England 2022), and other authors studying specific network-related tools such as online platforms (Kuhn and Galloway 2013), teaching-learning ecologies (Bailey and Barley 2010), and intermediaries (Comunian and England 2022). Often, studies on craft skills intertwine with analysis of higher education (Comunian and Gilmore 2016) and career formation (Luckman and Andrew 2020).

Generally, in the literature, skills are paired with other concepts such as mindset, **attitudes**, and internal motivations, which are considered central in “passion entrepreneurs” (Milanesi 2018 in Luckman and Andrew 2020) and in the case of “protean careers” (Hall 1996 in Luckman and Andrew 2020), meaning for individuals who pursue their creative practice driven by lifestyle or self-realization more than by market rewards. There seems to be a common acknowledgement that a certain attitude and strong motivation or passion are the main drivers to achieve a craft or creative career. They are not only drivers but attitudes or personal characteristics, such as relentless determination and motivation, which are portrayed as the necessary preconditions to start any career in the creative and craft sector. This common attitude may inform the result of some research (Frenette and Tepper in Comunian and Gilmore 2016) which found that art careers are very poor in the job market, but they have the happiest professionals.

Concerning **skills**, the article by Frenette and Tepper (Frenette and Tepper in Comunian and Gilmore 2016), even though it focuses on arts-based training and careers and not on craft, proposes a list of skills including a huge variety of competencies: from creative and critical thinking, problem-solving, artistic technique and research, broad knowledge and education, to leadership and project management skills, networking and persuasive speaking, clear writing, technological skills, entrepreneurial, financial and business skills. In their findings, art graduates, who are generally satisfied with the education received, argue that during their higher education, they acquired artistic techniques, project management and communication skills, with art schools being particularly effective in developing creative thinking and problem-solving capacities. However, they identify a lack of teaching, entrepreneurial, financial and business management skills in their art curricula. The skill mismatch offers a polarization of skills: on the one side, the financial and business-related ones are missing from art education, passing through more interpersonal skills such as networking, clear writing, leadership skills, and critical thinking which are acquired in a sort of indirect way, to the other side of the skills spectrum with artistic techniques,

creative thinking and broad knowledge as effectively taught in the art schools. The authors also study what proportion of graduate work in closely related fields, finding out that art careers are typically “boundaryless” and extend beyond one employer. A similar result is shown in England’s (2022) article on graduates entering the craft economy. She introduces the difference between skills and **resources**, the first being competencies that can be acquired with education and the latter as personal, contextual and structural characteristics of the individual, such as personal and support network, social capital, finances, machinery and all those resources that enable the physical making process or the establishment of professional status. In her findings, the highest-ranking skills - meaning the most important according to early-career craft professionals - are making skills followed by motivation, confidence and other intangible skills, communication, presentation, creative identity and interpersonal skills. Business-related and finance competencies were all given lower ranking. Regarding resources, hard infrastructure such as equipment and studio space were the highest-ranking ones, followed by soft infrastructure resources (access to opportunities) and support networks. As with the skills ranking, resources explicitly associated with business and money were given lower ratings than resources that enabled the physical making process and/or establishment of professional status.

In addition to these references, this research aims to study not only the early-career or graduate stage of the craft career but to analyse a broader sample of artisans at different stages of career, working in different ecosystems, with very different educational backgrounds. This difference is expected to highlight diverse needs in terms of skills and resources at different career stages and indications to build lifelong learning curricula.

Craft skills are strongly linked with **high educational paths** and also often influenced by the local **creative and cultural industries** in which they are inserted. CCIs and higher education institutions (HEI) have been studied as providers of soft infrastructure (networks), physical infrastructure (studio space, equipment, etc.), governance indications, and market opportunities to graduate craft students (England and Comunian in Comunian and Gilmore 2016). The relationship between training, teaching and learning within higher education and the realities emerging from established visual artists in a regional city has been investigated to understand how creative capital is mediated by the community of practice (Gilmore, Gledhill, Rajakovic in Comunian and Gilmore 2016). It emerged that during school and post-graduation artists are unprepared in the commercial aspect of their profession (i.e. promotion of their work, networking, applying to funding opportunities, organising exhibitions, communicating their work) and all of them have experienced precariousness that has pushed the majority to undertake part-time jobs in related and not-related artistic fields - this situation is expected to be very similar to that of the craft sector. Also Bridgstock and Cunningham (2016) highlight that the key problem for creative higher education is

the lack of entrepreneurial capabilities for arts students. It is also for this structural educational lack that craft makers are lifelong learners, which can be interpreted as a positive aspect if related to problem-solving and experimental skills, but also as a negative one if it reflects - as it seems - a poor initial education in key skill areas (Oakley et al 2008). This mirrors an unbalance between artistic/symbolic work and utilitarian/functional among artists that, in the case of the art field, is partly addressed by other commercial actors of the system such as galleries and collectors. In the case of craft commercial intermediaries are less present - if not entirely absent - and usually the craft maker needs to do both symbolic and functional work.

So, from the literature, it emerges that craft education and initial career stage are comparable with other creative careers, such as the artistic one, in terms of skills' competencies (mainly business-related and management ones) and boundaryless of work (both artists and craft makers at least at the initial stage need to carry on multiple jobs to maintain their practice). Both of them also share the same underlying working motivation based on passion, creativity, and self-expression rather than on market success or recognition. The study of their skills gaps and careers is strictly tied to higher education and to the creative district or city in which they are inserted.

Similar **European research projects** have been and are still being conducted addressing craft and craft skills. Among them, *Crafting Europe*, led by the Design & Crafts Council Ireland (DCCI) between 2019 and 2022, has published a report on new models for European crafts to build capacity within the craft sectors in Europe. It is co-funded by the Creative Europe Programme of the European Commission and it has nine partners: Artex (Italy), Crafts Council (United Kingdom), Limerick Institute of Technology (Ireland), CEARTE (Portugal), EOI Fundesarte (Spain), Crafts Council Netherlands, Handicrafts Chamber of Ukraine, Georgian Arts and Culture Centre (Georgia). The project is divided into three macro-areas: (a) crafting business, which is a professional training programme developed in response to a need to share expertise, building business skills and marketing strategies for makers; (b) iAtelier, a programme of activities that encourage innovation through the integration of technologies into traditional craft practices; (c) research to assess the economic impact of the craft sectors in Europe. Their key focus is to enhance new skills and improve the employability of emerging professionals in the craft sector, which is why it includes expert training and tutorials, seminars and collaborations between makers and designers. According to this study, the skills gap seems to tackle business-related competencies and technological innovation.

Another relevant European project is *Mosaic* (Mastering Job-Oriented Skills in Arts and craft thanks to Centres of vocational excellence), an Erasmus+ project involving 7 countries and 15 main partners that aims to improve vocational training in arts and crafts to meet the challenges posed by digital, environmental and socio-economic developments. It addresses specific key issues for vocational training schools and

companies dealing with crafts, tradition and creativity, among which the most important is the need for skills. It recently (2023) published a report on the skills for the arts and crafts sector, mapping the skill gaps in the project partner countries (France, Italy, Finland, Bulgaria, Canada, Armenia). Their study suggests that arts and crafts businesses have a real interest in social inclusion, digitalisation and sustainability topics, but they face a series of challenges in operationalizing them. According to the project, this difficulty can be overcome by developing specific skills related to self-development, entrepreneurship, digitalisation, cooperation and collaboration.

Tracks4Crafts is an ongoing European project, which examines and transforms the transmission of traditional crafts knowledge to enhance the societal and economic valuation of crafts and align them with a future-oriented heritage approach in Europe. The project aims to carry on its mission by transforming learning processes in physical spaces in which craftspeople collaborate, producing tools and instruments which enable capturing the value of traditional craft knowledge, and creating networks to foster and disseminate the societal and economic value of craft. The research is based on experiments in eight ecosystems.

Craeft (Craft Understanding, Education, Training, and Preservation for Posterity and Prosperity) is a European project that applies computer science techniques to the development of craft education and craft simulation. In particular, Craeft integrates haptics intelligence in digital design and connects tacit knowledge of craftsmen with the recovery of lost techniques. The use of digital technologies has the aim, among others, of supporting experimental craft simulation, and digitising movements and techniques for education purposes. The project developed an ethnographic protocol rationale that is based on the conjunction of anthropology of techniques, sociology of work and video elicitation methodology, which provides the recording of craft gestures and their potential use for educational purposes.

4. METHODOLOGY

The research started with a thorough literature review on skills, attitudes and resources of craft makers, which also informs this paper. The theoretical work was then paired with an empiric effort, based on the usual – and very informative – movement back and forth from theory to field and vice versa. Then the research leading to this deliverable took place through three main data collections, which correspond to the structure of this deliverable: first, the research units of the different universities involved in the project started conducting pilot interviews (see Section 5) on the themes relevant for the whole project, including the (possible) educational gaps perceived by the different craft-makers. Findings were then shared and discussed among researchers, in a process of collective sensemaking. Secondly, a questionnaire was developed specifically on the perceived educational and skills gaps (see Section 6), and distributed to craft-makers in Europe. Thirdly, the survey results were presented during a co-creation workshop in Dals Långed (March 2024) where the craft-makers were invited to confront and discuss them together with researchers (see Section 7).

Interviews were carried out on a collaborative basis by different research partners to minimise the travelling so as to be climate responsible and to avoid overwhelming craft-makers with too many interviews. The consortium decided to draft one common interview protocol, comprising all the relevant themes for all work packages. Then interviews were carried out in each ecosystem by the “local” research partners: Tor Vergata and Ca’ Foscari for Bassano del Grappa and Venezia, University of Gothenburg for Dals Långed and Fengersfors, Copenhagen Business School for Bornholm. Results are then shared between partners, and inform all work packages. Data is shared and stored according to the already deposited Data Management Plan (D7.1).

In Italy Interviews took place starting at the beginning of the summer and are still being carried on. The analysis started in October 2023, and the first preliminary results were used to challenge the list of relevant skills emerging from the literature. Regarding the ecosystems of Venezia and Bassano del Grappa, up to this moment we conducted 27 interviews (14 in Bassano/Nove and 13 in Venezia/Murano), lasting from one to three hours each. We also conducted two focus groups in the Ecosystem of Bassano del Grappa. In Dals Långed and Fengersfors the interviews conducted by the researchers of the University of Gothenburg are 35, and they are the basis for the section about the Swedish ecosystem in the next paragraph. As for Bornholm, interviews conducted so far are not enough to draw preliminary results scientifically solid enough to be included in this deliverable. The results, beyond being useful per se, are also the basis for the following step, which is an online questionnaire targeted at craft-makers. As expected, craft careers vary and depend on several variables such as the craft material, the local territory (city, village, metropolis, rural area, etc.), the social

dimension (isolation, collaborative community, etc.), and economic and fiscal aspects among others. So, the theoretical framework needs to be matched with data grounded in fieldwork research, since it needs to take into consideration the specificities of the local ecosystems. Grounding on both literature and exploratory pilot interviews, the skills scheme aims to suit different European ecosystems to gain a general collection of data and to produce a comparative analysis which will then inform the development of life-long learning curricula. We grouped the skills, attitudes and resources emerging from this phase into a framework of craft competencies used to draw the questionnaire. The research is based on the distinction between skills and resources and on the acknowledgement of the importance of certain attributes and attitudes in the symbolic construction and sense-making of craft careers. Differently from other studies, this research proposes a structured framework of skills and resources divided by competence areas and knowledge application.

The skills are divided into five macro-categories: (1) craft-making skills and technical skills indicating the mastery to work with a specific material; (2) technological skills meaning the capacity to adopt technological innovation in the working process; (3) business skills as the competences to know markets, manage costs, set prices, know the regulatory environment; (4) communication and selling skills including the ability to communicate on different selling platform the products; and (5) transversal skills intended as those skills ranging from cultural broad knowledge to professional network. A detailed list of each skill included in the macro categories is in Table 1

Table 2 - Detailed list of skills

Craft-making skills and technical skills	Mastery of technique, the ability to expertly work a specific material Artistic sensitivity and technique Creative research and experimentation Personal style Creative thinking and problem-solving
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Technological skills	<p>Automation and robotic production: the ability to digitise production steps, including through robotisation</p> <p>Digitisation: the digitisation of part of the production process</p> <p>3D printing/modelling: the use of 3D printing or modelling</p> <p>AI interaction: the use of artificial intelligence embedded in processing steps</p> <p>Research /Experimentation skills: the ability to test solutions by exploiting technological innovation</p>
Business skills	<p>Business models /business plan</p> <p>Entrepreneurship and market analysis</p> <p>Leadership, recruiting collaborators and education</p> <p>Project management skills/ Time management</p> <p>Financial and accounting skills</p> <p>IP legal knowledge</p>
Communication and selling skills	<p>Marketing and promotion: the ability to communicate and promote your product</p> <p>Social Media management / e-commerce: the ability to communicate and sell your product online</p> <p>Creative identity/Brand/Presentation: the ability to effectively communicate the identity and originality of one's product</p> <p>Sales: communication and client management</p> <p>Pricing</p>
Transversal skills	<p>Networking skills (both professional and personal): the ability to create and exploit a network of colleagues and producers</p> <p>Cultural awareness/Broad knowledge and education: Broad cultural competence and the capacity for lifelong learning</p> <p>Critical thinking, dedication, motivation: the individual's aptitude for critical thinking and motivation</p> <p>Sustainability green and circular economy expertise</p>

The subdivision of skills helps in better analysing the perceived lacks and gaps in competencies, tracing skills back to educational pathways, eventually proposing new curricula, and understanding how different skills are transmitted and taught (directly or indirectly) in the schools and the field. For instance, craft-making skills are usually described as situated learning, meaning that learning occurs contextually as individuals participate in the community of practice, which is why apprenticeship in professionals' studios is the most diffused form of craft-making learning. Technological skills or business-related ones, instead, are taught more directly or explicitly (e.g. information seeking, courses, etc.).

The resources are in this case juxtaposed to the skills in a relational way, asking craft makers which skill they need to acquire or develop to enhance their resources. The resources identified are again divided into macro-categories: (1) financial resources such as funding opportunities, favourable tax accounting, etc.; (2) personal or support network including friends and family supporting the craft career; (3) material support as the availability of machinery, materials and studio space; and (4) professional network as the access to advice from peers and to career development opportunities. Also, in this case, the sub-division of resources in different areas makes it easier to address them in relation to skills.

The skills and resources macro structure aims to not only provide a hierarchy of perceived useful/less skills but also to identify skill gaps and to understand which skills need to be acquired by the craft maker and which ones can be outsourced to other professionals, platforms or services.

While the original plan was to target only the craft-makers within Hephaestus Ecosystems, we then considered targeting a wider audience of craft-makers, since we are in any case able to distinguish between results from the different ecosystems. Also, we decided to leave the questionnaire open after the delivery of this report, to keep collecting data throughout the whole life of the project, and distribute updates on the questionnaire's results. The questionnaire is reachable at the address <http://tinyurl.com/hephaestus-quest> or through the QR code in Fig. 1

Therefore, the questionnaire was distributed to craft makers, both students and professionals, living in different parts of Europe (with a specific focus on the ecosystems) to map the problems in terms of skills, training courses, curricula, adoption of new technologies, and challenges they face from higher education through their ongoing career.

The questionnaire was created using Microsoft Office Forms, which is compliant to the data rules within the Horizon Europe Framework. The questionnaire was developed in Italian and English, since we understood from project partners that craft-makers in Bornholm and Dals Långed were English speakers, while craft-makers in Italy on average are not fluent in English. At the very beginning of the questionnaire, respondents are asked whether they would like to leave name, surname, and address, to be contacted during the development of the Hephaestus projects for updates and

results distribution. Respondents who accepted to leave this personal information had to explicitly accept sharing this personal data, after reading a GDPR-compliant informed consent written by the Data Protection Officer of the University of Rome Tor Vergata. Nonetheless, to prioritise the diffusion of the questionnaire, it was also possible to answer without providing name and email. In this case, though, as the info regarding the ecosystem the respondents pertain to is mandatory, we were in any case able to conduct analyses based on how respondents from different ecosystems answered.

Figure 1- Questionnaire QR code

As for the distribution of the questionnaire, local partners were responsible for sharing it among craft-makers in their ecosystems. We have decided to proceed in this manner and not to directly send emails or make phone calls to all the craft-makers, in order to balance two objectives of the utmost importance. On one hand, it is important for us to maximise the number of responses to the questionnaire. On the other hand, however, all the partners responsible for disseminating the questionnaire (University of Gothenburg, BOFA, Ca' Foscari University of Venice) have expressed concern that excessive pressure on the artisans could damage relationships that have been painstakingly built, even over the years. In other words, artisans (as we will see later in discussing the responses to the questionnaire) greatly value their time, which is the most valuable - but also the scarcest - resource they have, and they like to select how to use their time. Indeed, more than one craft-maker, especially in Denmark, has expressed some discomfort towards an unpaid use of their time. Furthermore, the craft-makers of the Hephaestus ecosystems are subject to many requests for

interaction: interviews, questionnaires, focus groups, participation in research as ambassadors, and the local partners felt it was appropriate for them to mediate in the distribution of the questionnaire. However, they have all been very willing to distribute it, even though, as a BOFA partner told us, we must also accept that the craft-makers may not want to respond to our questionnaire.

To maximise the distribution of the questionnaire, it was decided to also use trade associations, which are part of the project and have a good rooting in the territory, as accelerators. In particular, for this task we relied on Italian craft associations of CNA Venezia, Confartigianato Venezia, Confartigianato Vicenza and their associates and related projects (i.e. Venice Original). For the other ecosystems, the ambassadors were targeted with a similar request, to help spread the questionnaire thanks to the strength of their social ties within the local communities.

We provided partners, ambassadors and local associations with the link to the questionnaire and an introductory text to be used in the email, and we asked the partners to also send follow-up reminders: Italian and Swedish partners sent the questionnaire at least twice, whereas Danish partners only once. In this case, we needed to balance our interest in collecting more answers and the need for local partners to safeguard their relationship with ambassadors and not to stress them too much. The questionnaire was also published on the Hephaestus website and social media (Instagram, Facebook) twice. Moreover, the questionnaire was also sent to similar European projects and their members, to leverage the networks of craft-makers created by these projects, and to institutions working with craft-makers in Europe. In particular, we involved in the distribution the teams of the following projects: Crafting Europe (<https://www.craftingeurope.com/>), Mad'in Europe (<https://www.madineurope.eu/it/>), World Crafts Council Europe (<https://wcc-europe.org/>), Track4Crafts (<https://tracks4crafts.eu/>), Craeft (<https://www.craeft.eu/>), Colour4craft (<https://www.helsinki.fi/en/researchgroups/bio-based-colourants/about-colour4crafts>), Aarhus University research project on sustainable fashion (<https://arts.au.dk/en/news-and-events/news/show/artikel/forskningsprojekt-skal-goere-modeindustrien-mere-baeredygtig>), which have spread it to their craft-makers and members.

Before moving on to the commentary of the results, we must add a further note. We decided to construct the sample of respondents from the bottom up, and not from lists of categories or market codes because, as highlighted by Cacciatore and Panozzo (2022), with reference to the Veneto case, many artistic activities do not have an ATECO code (Istat classification of economic activities) and are not listed in the official statistics. Essentially, as more thoroughly described in the Deliverable 6.6 of the Hephaestus Project (Cacciatore and De Bernard, 2024), the existing classification systems fail to adequately represent crafting organizations. While traditional categorizations effectively delineate conventional economic activities, they falter when

applied to craft. The deliverable analyses NACE and its national equivalents – ATECO, SNI, and Dansk Branchekode DB07 - for Italy, Sweden, and Denmark, respectively. Craft, due to its unique characteristics, often gets lumped into industrial and mass-produced manufacturing sectors, despite its distinct nature. Operating predominantly through micro-enterprises in informal settings, craft defies rigid definitions, emphasizing process over final product and eluding straightforward classification. As a consequence, any policy or mapping based on such classification systems risk failing to address the specific needs of craft organizations, and without accurate classification, policies and regulations prove ill-fitted for crafters, hindering rather than facilitating their activities. As the definitions of craft-makers have not the same meaning in different ecosystems, and there are generally no code-based clear definitions of what and who falls into the art craft sector, instead of using partial lists of artisans, held together by an administrative classification that does not necessarily reflect reality, we preferred a grounded approach and we started from those who truly know the craft makers, being able to select only those of interest for the project. As a result, the craft-makers who received the link to the questionnaire were indicated by one of the Hephaestus partners or came from the lists of craft-maker associations mentioned above, or were indicated by projects similar to Hephaestus. Finally, we asked the artisans who had responded to the questionnaire to forward it to other craft-makers like them, to also carry out a snowball addition.

The questionnaire was available online from 22 December 2023 and so far (as of 9th March 2024) we collected 78 answers. Even if not requested by the project, we will provide an updated version of the deliverable once we collect more answers and data.

5. INTERVIEWS

5.1 Bassano del Grappa and Venezia

Even though Venice and Bassano del Grappa represent two different ecosystems, within Hephaestus, in this paragraph we will treat them together because, from the interviews, no significant difference emerged among the artisans regarding their educational backgrounds, apprenticeships, and skills possessed or desired. The main differences concern the market size and the international strength of Venice's brand as a tourist location, but these topics are only tangential to the content of this deliverable.

Figure 2 - A craft-maker and her loom

Formal Education

The interviewed craft-makers do not have standard curricula or common educational backgrounds: some of them have an artistic education in the Academy of Fine Arts or artistic high schools, whereas others have radically different educational paths outside the craft or artistic world (e.g., languages, engineering, mechanics, chemistry, etc.), and some of them, especially those with an artistic background, have studied abroad

(Netherlands, Belgium, France). However, regarding educational profiles, many artisans have had specific training in the techniques relevant to the material they work with. This often occurred in dedicated schools: "I went to study lutherie at [the Civic School of] Milan," others trained at the Academy of Fine Arts, or attended courses at professional schools. In Nove, in the province of Bassano, the State Art Institute Luigi de Fabris is a high school that has played a significant role for generations in training people who would be employed in the ceramic sector. And this happened in a town - Nove - that after the Second World War had about 5,000 inhabitants, about 160 companies or individual businesses in the ceramic sector, and about 4,600 employed in the sector. Then, according to the interviewees, also because the work in ceramics was seen as hard and poorly paid, many young people turned to jobs in a nearby mechanical district, characterised by contracts that are framed by a more advantageous National Labor Contract. Moreover, competition on lower-priced product ranges has led to the closure of many businesses in Nove, where, however, those who manage to do artisanal work with added value flourish. However, as much as the artisans' experiences vary in terms of the duration of their studies, all of them have had at least specific technical training: "My path was quite simple because I went to the art institute here in Nove. I didn't do 5 years, I did three years and then I left because I was not a great student, unlike my brothers who are all accountants [...] In 1984 you could still find a job." Often, moreover, we find this narrative that technical school, or art school, should be paths suited to people who do not do particularly well in school: "I studied at the art institute, so here in Nove. Let's say that school was not really my place, where I felt most comfortable, so I always had a bit of difficulty up to high school and so let's say the choice was directed towards something more manual, where I could better express what I felt inside. So I started the art institute and there I really found my dimension, but in the field of design, not so much in painting or sculpture, but precisely in the design of objects. So I do something useful for people, or that brings well-being both from a functional point of view, but also from a purely emotional point of view. There I discovered a world and I started to like school. And from there I decided to continue. I studied three years at ISIA in Pordenone industrial design and then I moved to Milan for the other two years at the Polytechnic, always in the field of industrial product innovation." Or, again, on formal studies: "my story begins with a school path that I always remember with great joy: The Polytechnic School of Design in Milan. Meanwhile, I would have found an international environment because the students were from different countries [...] a school that gave me a decisive imprint, in the sense that it taught me to design, to see, to design three-dimensional objects, to position objects in a certain space. Even using all that knowledge even now, on visual perception, on physiology." Next to school, the factory also plays a fundamental role for artisans. Factory that, in common feeling, is an artisan factory, because the work is done with tools and hands, and because the products are unique pieces, whether it is glass or ceramics. The factory serves to give skills and also discipline: "My dad had a

ceramics workshop [at home]. After I finished the art institute my dad told me 'you don't come to work here right away. Go to the factory for 4-5 years, see how it works and what it means to take your pay at the end of the month, start working at the right hours and finish at the right hours'. Not that when you stay at home you get up at 9. Anyway, in the factory for 3-4 years and after I decide when you stay at home.' I went to the factory, I did two years, I did the military, then I returned to the factory. After a year or two he told me, 'now you can stay at home'. Or, in the experience of another craftswoman, the furnace plays an indispensable role: "actually I started working because I was flunked in high school. My father [...] told me No, you're out, you don't feel like doing, I send you to the furnace, which is like sending the child to the factory. It's unbearable, you realise that you even sweat at the knees. [...] And then [I liked it] and in September I decided to switch to evening classes and continue working glass. [...] I worked in glass from 15 to 17 years old in Murano, then. First in the factory in the furnace, then with a master." And then, often mentioned as a source of learning is the family: often even those who have done different studies have learned a craft thanks to artisan parents or grandparents: "I did all sorts of stuff in my whole life [...] I studied, I graduated and in the meantime I worked in catering, I worked in tourism, in short, a lot of jobs [...] the approach I had had to ceramics was when my dad took me when I was little to the factory and while he worked on the press he gave me the ceramics and I made violins, I made little caterpillars, those things that kids do." Indeed, in some cases, the creative district in which they were born and raised influenced their career, as a craft entrepreneur in Nove said: "I never went to art school or anything else, however, I'm from Nove, I grew up in this ceramic working environment that you breathed willy-nilly". For many of them, the family tradition of craft-making was decisive in choosing a craft career, both because they already knew the material or the working environment, and because they inherited an already established laboratory and business. Finally, the other mode of learning is through non-university courses, mainly at artisans. Also working for other artisans is a source of learning often mentioned in interviews. Overall, interviews suggest the importance of training through good schooling and practical work experience. Several times the fact that the ceramic curriculum in the high school was eventually closed was pinpointed as a major issue affecting the field, but at the same time the Director of the State Art Institute Luigi de Fabris in Nove told us that the curriculum was closed once, then they tried opening it again. Then it was eventually closed for lack of interest, as not enough students enrolled.

Figure 4 - Arcicuchi (big whistles) in ceramic

Management and Communication

But if all the artisans seem satisfied with the technical training they have received, and the artisanal skills that improve every day through working and working, it is in the area of management and communication that they lament the greatest lack of skills. Technical and material mastery is necessary but not sufficient to become a good craft-maker, as the importance of design as creative projectuality is also fundamental to innovate the current production. Among the skills that are perceived as most missing they mentioned communication skills (i.e., managing social media profiles, photographing their productions, creating a website, etc.), and promotional skills (i.e., managing and communicating with clients, extending their client base, selling their products on dedicated platforms). There are also business skills such as pricing and making a budget (i.e., understanding how much the craft activity costs, how much it costs to produce a single product and how much people can spend for it). Almost unanimously all the craft-makers stated that doing craft - regardless of the material - is a lifelong learning activity, meaning that they constantly learn new techniques or experiment with new procedures and new products. Having the possibility to focus only on learning craft is the preferred option of many craft-makers who would prefer having

other collaborators/services to deal with the communication or business aspect of the job. A weaver said: "I know I am very lacking in some aspects of client management. Social management can be improved, but I know I have an age that has objective limitations, I mean. But I actually find it more enjoyable, nicer to focus on some things than others." The theme that links communication, pricing, and selling echoes in the words of many artisans. Several craft-makers lament they do not have the time and/or skills for running social media, which are paramount ("if I did not have Instagram, I would not exist as a craft-maker"). But as they lack skills in Social Media Management, they also dream about outsourcing this task. "I don't know if it's a lack of skills or just a lack of time, but maybe it's a bit of both, which is the communication part. We are a disaster, a disaster, that is we don't have a website, we don't have [...] it takes an external vision that helps us to clarify many things that are there and that perhaps we struggle to filter [...] communication, social media, those things give us a bit of hives [...] we like to do, we like to think and experiment, so the whole communication part is really something that no, absolutely not, we don't get it." Or also: "the part in which I definitely struggle more because it's not mine is the whole marketing part. It's very difficult for me, I had to learn it. I'm very reluctant to do it. But it has to be done. The whole part of understanding what it means to make an Instagram page, to keep the Instagram page all coordinated. What to write on the Instagram page, how many stories to make and how to make them. How much to follow up on Facebook? The site." In this context, however, the experience of a craftswoman who, having studied photography, can take professional photos of her works, with great satisfaction, must be emphasised: "I decided it was easier because of the workload to do it alone, having obviously the skills [...] You decide that you have four products, four colors, taking those photos there bores me a lot. But to think that every time I come out with a new collection I have 70 pieces to photograph, calling a photographer every time also becomes costly. [...] And so this allows me to do everything by myself". Mentions of technological innovation and digitization as well deal with communication, as digitalization is described as something useful to increase the online presence through specific marketplaces (e-commerce). If craft-makers think of digitalization, most often they refer to the last processes within the value chain, and not to the design and production process. However, managing digital channels and online presence requires specific skills that not all craft-makers possess.

Concerning resources, there was not a diffused explicit awareness of the family support in terms of continuity of the craft activity (sometimes it was presented more as a burden) or in terms of facilities, such as having a studio in the family house or acquired by a parent, but they were presented as a taken-for-granted condition that was fundamental for the continuity of their activity.

creativity through the organisation of seminars and workshops, or sometimes as the collaboration between a craft maker and a designer or artist: “there was a need to go and collaborate with different figures, first of all a designer who could design contemporary objects or collections”. Other craft makers have interpreted this external gaze as a design competence they learnt at university: “From my point of view, the design idea is the most important thing. And let's say that a great technical knowledge is not always accompanied by a beautiful design. So let's say that technique is a tool, it's a tool to realise some things, that's it. Technique as an end in itself, technical exercise can also be a bit sterile”. This external gaze can only bring strong innovations in materials and processes. In this regard, the case of two artisans who produce ceramic sex toys, using for some phases of the work skills present in the territory of Nove (outsourcing some tasks to other highly skilled artisans), is interesting. They have never encountered hostility for the type of product they make, but yes for the type of processing. In fact, no other craftsman has ever considered it inappropriate to introduce the use of ceramics for sex toys, but many artisans have commented negatively on the idea of glazing the porcelain, something that the craftswomen wanted to do for aesthetic reasons. Porcelain is already a noble material, therefore porcelain cannot be glazed. When instead the external glaze serves to experiment with techniques (for example, two craftswomen use algae from the Lagoon and the Brenta in the preparation of special clays), this experimentation is not only well received, but fully fits into the groove of a tradition by which the artisan learns by experimenting on the job daily.

Figure 6 - The workshop of a craft-maker

Other jobs

It must then be considered that several of the interviewees have another job, beyond the one as a craft-maker. Several are the reasons cited to explain the need for other jobs, and the kinds of jobs selected: often they just do not make a living out of craft-making, and to avoid spoiling their image with products designed only for the audience, they prefer to earn money in a different way, also to enjoy more their artistic/craft activity. Several craft-makers are teachers in universities, in high schools, or for craft courses. Other craft-makers do the most diverse jobs: from production on behalf of others, to having employment with other craft-makers, to having jobs that have nothing to do with the craft. An artisan, for example, works three days a week in a bar, because this guarantees her livelihood and completely frees her creativity from material aspects. Moreover, doing manual work can exercise lateral thinking and she can be more creative in her production of glass jewellery.

Artisan vs artist

Craft-makers mainly define themselves as “artisans” (i.e., someone who produces objects with a function, in limited series even if they produce unique pieces since they are all handmade, according to the definitions they provided), but some of them define their profession or those of *maestri* (i.e., someone who reaches an excellent level of making things, mainly technical skills) as “artists”. And this is true also for people performing only part of the artisanal process within big craft-making enterprises. According to their description, an artisan is a problem solver for the architect/artist/designer because he knows every step of the making process. Indeed, some of the people interviewed are not happy because craft-making is considered less than art, while others feel comfortable as artisan and not as artists: “No, I'm not an artist, I'm an artisan, I work to live and to support my family, basically. When they tell me ‘artist’... the artist is something else, I don't invent anything strange, I do very popular things. The artist is someone who has imagination, who makes somewhat strange things, who does things outside of the norm.”

Figure 7 - Tools of a craft-maker

Network

Another of the themes that emerges, when talking about skills, is that of the network of artisans. On the one hand, usually, craft-makers search for competencies that they do not have, i.e., design, or they search for a skilled artisan for a specific task. On the

other hand, friendship comes with intellectual property protection (“here we are all friends, but my secrets are my secrets”), and several interviewed complained that the Nove district would have/would benefit from some forms of collaborative actions (e.g. research centre) or network-making efforts. Apparently, similar initiatives in the past, that regarded a much more industrial context, failed because of the near-sightedness of the entrepreneurs that did not want to spend money beyond their own activity. Elaborating on the situation regarding the contemporary crafting scene of Nove, another craft-maker also complained that collaborative initiatives (some of which he himself contributed to) are not frequent because, he argued, suspicion towards peers, in terms of sharing your techniques, may come in the way. To this extent, a certain distance seems to exist between an individualism characterising the Italian ecosystems, and a collectivism characterising Dals Långed. Reasons can depend on cultural differences, or maybe individualism results from the failure of a once-successful industrial district. Is it plausible that, whilst the niche and “never-booming” Swedish crafts always “struggled”, needing thus from the start some forms of collaborative actions, the crafters of Nove are still in the long wave of the district golden age when, at least for a while, to work autonomously was economically sustainable. That said, craft-makers seem to be open to different forms of collaboration, and seem eager to build a network among peers to foster collaborations with different craft-makers (with different skills) to carry on common processes (e.g., social media, selling, work management), with other professionals (e.g., university students for communication), and also for practical collaborations (on materials, instruments, competencies).

Education

In the end, craft-makers seem to be aware of the skills they lack, but they do not seem to be completely aware of how to improve skills through education and training, also because of a lack of time which is mentioned several times. One craft-maker highlighted the importance of school training and continuous learning, but also the importance of hands-on learning, highlighting her experience of learning through working in her aunt's weaving workshop. But most craft-makers affirm that they do not have time and money for education, but mostly time, as they need to keep producing always. Nonetheless, some recognize that entrepreneurship, marketing, and soft skills would be great to improve, but they said so only after we went through a long paraphrase to formulate the questions, since the answer to the direct question was that “she has no time to learn”. Other craft-makers improve their skills almost unconsciously, and they recognize their path only in the interview-enhanced sense-making process, as the first answer regarding how they improve their skills is “I just live my life.” Overall, what emerges from the interviews is the acknowledgement from

the craft-makers of a lack of skills, especially business and communication ones, which is associated with a perceived lack of time to acquire them. Since the craft-making activity is generally time-consuming, the craft-makers prefer to invest their time in the “core production” rather than investing in developing collateral competencies, which sometimes are not perceived as in line with their attitude. In this case, the craft-makers either do not use that skill/service (e.g., no social media communication, no e-commerce, no business plan) or outsource it to relatives and friends, if possible. This signals a gap in competencies and a possibility for future professionals to provide a service or collaborate with makers (e.g., the incubator, the business developer, the communication strategist).

5.2 Dals Långed and Fengersfors¹

Competences and learning needs in the craft ecosystem Dals Långed and Fengersfors. *Background*

Many of the craft makers in this Swedish ecosystem are educated at a post-high school educational institution, specialised in crafts, arts and/or design. In Sweden the main options for craft education after high school are two: Folk Högskolan (Folk High School) and the Academy of Art. The Folk High School, a common institution in the Nordic countries and in the German-speaking parts of Europe, is a professional education institution that can be attended after completing high school and does not lead to an academic diploma, like a bachelor degree. The Academies of Art are higher education institutions that are equivalent to universities and operate under the Higher Education Law. Many of the Swedish Academies are part of universities, like the Academy of Art and Design at the University of Gothenburg (HDK-Valand), which has developed through a process of inclusion of different Academies (of Design and Craft, Fine Arts, Film and Photography) in the Artistic Faculty at the University of Gothenburg.

In Dals Långed, one educational environment is particularly important for the craft makers’ community: Steneby. At the premises of Steneby, there are two educational institutions: One is the Steneby School, which is a Folk High School, and the other one is the Steneby unit of the Academy of Art and Design at the University of Gothenburg. The main materials which are in focus at Steneby are metal, wood and textile. Both schools have an attractive power for those interested in learning craft locally and nationally and, as part of the Academy of Art and Design at the University of Gothenburg, the Steneby unit also attracts many international students. Some of them stay after education, thus contributing to the local community.

¹ paragraph written by Elena Raviola

Steneby has also an important standing in the local community as an employer. In fact, both schools employ on a more or less stable basis local craft makers as teachers. Most of the staff working in both schools at Steneby have a background as a craft maker and only very few teachers at the Steneby unit of the Academy have a research degree, thus focusing the education on practice-based learning and taking advantage of the large workshops at the premises.

Based on our interviews and interactions with the local community of craft makers, we summarise here the educational gaps and competence needs as they are perceived.

Managing a fragmented professional life

From our interviews, one of the main findings is that most of the craft makers' professional life is fragmented across different jobs. Some of these jobs are related to their craft, for example teaching, and some others are not, for example working at the bakery or in other retail stores. Juggling between these different jobs and their different seasonality is not easy for the craft makers both in terms of time and focus for their craft work. One need we see is therefore to have professional development tools that psychologically and practically help the craft makers to handle the fragmentation. This could address the need for better learning time management and handling the stress of their vocational aspiration vis-à-vis their fragmented professional reality.

New technologies

Many of the craft makers we have interacted with in the local community have expressed that they work by making with their hands and only use manual tools. They are proud of handmaking, which allows them to control the whole process of crafting from the raw material to the final product, but some of them express their curiosity and need to learn more about new technologies. This is driven not necessarily by the wish to scale up their production significantly, but by the desire to innovate, increase efficiency in some of the tasks and make new things. New technologies are exemplified by 3D printing and CNC machines.

Recently, in the area an initiative has been established to experiment with wood furniture production. It is called Open Wood and is located on the premises of a dismantled paper factory which was left empty. At this premises, the local regional development initiative and company Motesplats Steneby has established a sort of laboratory with CNC machines and other machines to experiment on wood. This place

also serves as a meeting point sometimes and it could be an avenue to further develop a new technology craft lab on these premises.

Business development

All craft makers we have met have their own business. Most of them are independent businesses that have relationships with each other and are limited in growth by their very craft practice. Most of the craft makers express that they did not learn any business-related subject in school and therefore had to learn everything related to their business, for example accounting, intellectual property and administration, when they started their business after school.

Business development is thus an area of skill development which would be needed in education, aimed not at making crafts students experts in business, but making them able to make informed business decisions and have an informed dialogue with business people, for example accountants.

Collaboration with other industries and professions

Finally, one area of development that some craft makers mention can be seen as the expansion of craft in other sectors and areas of society, thus collaborating with other occupations and professions. There are for example many craft makers whose crafts are relevant in construction and architectural design or in landscape architecture as well as in participatory processes for social inclusion. While craft-makers learn during their professional life to expand their craft as a way to develop their business, it would be beneficial to address the competencies needed both on a practical and theoretical level to make this expansion. This would probably need a long-term engagement in skill development and sharing and discussing with others in the community as well as researchers and experts to experiment and innovate.

6. QUESTIONNAIRE

The questionnaire is structured according to the division of skills into five macro-categories: (1) craft-making skills and technical skills indicating the mastery to work with a specific material; (2) technological skills meaning the capacity to adopt technological innovation in the working process; (3) business skills as the competences to know markets, manage costs, set prices, know the regulatory environment; (4) communication and selling skills including the ability to communicate on different selling platform the products; and (5) transversal skills intended as those skills ranging from cultural broad knowledge to professional network. These are paired with resources which are again divided into macro-categories: (a) financial resources such as funding opportunities, favourable tax accounting, etc.; (b) personal or support network including friends and family supporting the craft career; (c) material support as the availability of machinery, materials and studio space; and (d) professional network as the access to advice from peers and to career development opportunities. The questionnaire is then divided into five major sections: (i) anagraphic, (ii) craft-making, (iii) ranking of the most important competencies and resources, (iv) training vs outsourcing, and (v) final open questions about education and training. The (i) anagraphic collects data on the respondent such as nationality, gender, typology of the school attended and education training, and perceived missed educational gaps. The second section on (ii) craft-making is accessible only to craft makers who currently have an activity and not to students. It addresses the professional activity of the craft maker asking for the definition of the profession, the duration of the craft activity/career, which material is used, if the respondent has parents who already had a craft activity, the presence of collaborators/employees, and the property of a studio as a workplace. It also investigates if the respondent's only source of revenue comes from the craft job or if he/she has other jobs, related or not related to the craft sector. The market aspect is also taken into account by asking which selling channels the craft maker uses and his/her participation in fairs. The (iii) ranking of the most important competencies and resources is based on the division of skills into categories, as aforementioned, and it allows the respondent to hierarchize the macro-skills and macro-resources and to rate them in detail. The ranking and rating as a research tool is used also by other scholars (England 2022) and it reflects the perceived importance of specific skills from the point of view of the respondent. The part on (iv) training and outsourcing is a way to reflect on which of these skills the respondent is available to spend time and energy, and on which he/she prefers someone else to do it. This question mits us to understand which skills are considered fundamental to personally control/achieve and which ones are important for the job but not for the individual craft maker. The conclusive part (v) is composed of open facultative questions on educational gaps, possible training and challenges in acquiring new competencies.

6.1 Anagraphic

The majority of respondents, on a total of 78 answers, are aged between 46-55 and 56-65 years old, followed by a younger group of under 40, a very small group of people over 64 and just one person aged between 18-25 years old (Fig. 8). The majority of respondents are females (65%), while only 32% are males (Fig. 9).

Figure 8 - Questionnaire results. Age

Figure 9 - Questionnaire results. Gender

Concerning nationality, we collected more answers from Italian craft-makers (35%), while the Swedish and Danish contributions count respectively for 15% and 14%. A significant part (36%) of respondents has a different nationality from the ones indicated, ranging from Russia, Romania, Turkey, France, Portugal, Ireland, Spain, Iceland, Hungary, Canada, Austria, America, Germany.

Figure 10 - Questionnaire results. Nationality

Confronting nationality (Fig. 10) with their current living location, it emerged that 38% of respondents are based in Italy, 21% are based in Sweden, 17% in Denmark, and the remaining 24% are based in other European countries (Fig. 11). 87% of these people have lived in these countries for more than 15 years (Fig. 12). A small percentage (6%) have lived in the country for 6-10 years, and 4% have recently moved in (from 0 to 5 years). So the majority of respondents have been based in the place they live for a large part of their lives and are part of the local population.

Figure 11- Questionnaire results. In which country do you live?

Figure 12 - Questionnaire results. Since how many years do you live in this country?

Family composition is a very relevant characteristic because it permits us to understand if the craft-maker has some personal network and can count on economic support (e.g. sharing rent and costs) from family members. The majority of respondents (73%) live with a partner or their family and 24% live alone (Fig. 6).

Figure 13 - Questionnaire results. How many people compose your family unit?

The respondents' group is formed for 14% by students and 86% by professionals. When asked if they perceived any educational gap in their formation, 64% answered "no" and 36% "yes". The latter specified that the skills they especially lack are craft techniques ("The education focuses on having an artistic expression, not to learn how to wheel throw, cast, learn the true skills of the materials"), business and market competencies ("Learning about how to use my skills to sell products or services") and collaborative and professional approaches.

As can be seen from the figures below (Fig. 13, Fig. 14), the highest level of education achieved is a university level (bachelor's and master's degree), followed by a high school diploma. Few of the respondents have a post-graduate master or PhD, and only 3 have a middle school diploma from a professional school.

Figure 14 - Questionnaire results. What is the highest level of education you have obtained?

Figure 15 - Questionnaire results. What kind of school did you attend or are you attending?

However, education levels vary in different countries, highlighting different craft curricula. For instance, in Italy the craft makers’ more diffused level of education is high school (34%), followed by professional schools (23%), university degree counts for 17% and art schools for 13%. Indeed, in Italy, art schools’ diplomas (i.e. Accademie di Belle Arti) are still not equated to universities’ degrees, reflecting an institutional division between applied arts and theoretical knowledge (Fig. 16).

ITALY - KIND OF SCHOOL ATTENDED

- Art Institute ■ University ■ Professional school ■ High school
- Technical Institute ■ Other/Apprendistato ■ Prefer not to answer

Figure 16 - Questionnaire results. Education in Italy

On the contrary, Sweden (Fig. 17), Denmark (Fig. 18) and other countries (Fig. 19) have a large majority of craft-makers with a university title (Sweden 67%, Denmark 100%, Other 89%). This is also due to the fact that art schools are equated to universities in both countries, where artistic research grants and PhD are a reality that does not exist in Italy.

SWEDEN - KIND OF SCHOOL ATTENDED

- University ■ Specialistic course ■ Prefer not answer ■ High School

Figure 17 - Questionnaire results. Education in Sweden

DENMARK - KIND OF SCHOOL ATTENDED

Figure 18 - Questionnaire results. Education in Denmark

OTHERS - KIND OF SCHOOL ATTENDED

Figure 19 - Questionnaire results. Education in Other countries

Looking at the faculties chosen by the craft-makers who have a university degree, in Italy we find industrial design, economics, engineering, and management for culture. In Sweden and Denmark it is mainly Design with some specialisation based on the craft material or technique (ceramics, textile, knitting and embroidery). A greater diversity of subjects can be found in Italy, signalling maybe that craft was not the first choice for a job and a career.

Moreover, this educational difference may also be informative of the idea of craft in the different countries: in Italy it is perceived as mainly decorative and based on traditional knowledge which you can learn outside of universities, whereas in Nordic countries craft is associated with artistic research and it is critically theorised as design.

6.2 Craft-making as a profession

This section investigates the characteristics of craft as a profession, starting from its definition: as it can be seen in the graphic below (Fig. 20), the most used term is “designer”, followed by the Italian “artigiano”, highlighting again the different perception of the craft-maker as more related to design and projectuality, or more traditional and based in handmade production.

Figure 20 - Questionnaire results. How do you define your profession/job title?

The craft makers work with a huge variety of materials, from ceramics, textile, wood, paper, and metal as the main ones, to glass, stone, precious metals, precious stones, leather, and wax among others (Fig. 21). 47% of them have a craft working experience of more than 20 years, 22% of 11-20 years, 14% of 6-10 years, and 12% of less than 5 years (Fig. 22).

Figure 21 - Questionnaire results. What material(s) do you work with?

Figure 22 - Questionnaire results. How long have you been working with this material?

Family legacy is important also in connection with a craft career because it can provide already established markets, a professional network, in addition to material support such as a studio or technical machinery. 54% of the respondents’ families do not have a craft job, 34% have a professional craft-maker in their families, and 12% of them as a non-professional craft-maker (i.e. a hobbyist) in their families (Fig. 23). There is a significant continuity (67,6%) between the material used by the family member (usually the parents) and the material used by the craft-maker, so the family legacy is very impacting in the choice of the specific craft material.

Figure 23 - Questionnaire results. Is someone from your family (or even just one of your parents or relatives) an artisan?

For 59% of respondents craft is their main source of income, whereas the remaining 41% have another job through which they can sustain their craft activity (Fig. 24). Among these, only 3% have a second job in the same craft sector, whereas the majority of them have it in another sector (48%) or other (42%), as in Fig. 18. Those who work in the same craft sector are artists, freelance, or craft teachers. Those who work in different sectors or in other options, have a variety of different jobs, such as teaching at university, working in the ticket office of a museum, being a house assistant, a language teacher, an electrician, a company employee, or a public sector's employee.

The majority of craft-makers (70%) work autonomously and only 25% have collaborators (5% other). This gives us an indication of the very small size of the businesses we are intercepting.

Figure 24 - Questionnaire results. Is craft work your main source of income?

Figure 25 - Questionnaire results. What other jobs do you do besides being a craft-maker?

Concerning the studio space, the majority of the craft-makers (22) have a personal studio that they own, 15 craft-makers have a personal studio that they rent, 18 craft-makers do not have a studio and carry on their craft activity in their home, only 5 craft-makers share a studio with other ones, 5 of them have an industrial plant (Fig. 26), which can be intended as a craft company. Craft companies will be discussed in Section 8.

Figure 26 - Questionnaire results. Your studio/workshop, where you produce craft products

Among the most common selling channels is the physical shop, followed by fairs, online dedicated platforms and e-commerce. It is interesting to note that some craft-makers do not sell their products (Fig. 27). Among the most attended fairs, the Christmas local ones are the most frequently cited, together with local craft fairs, and a few specialised fairs (Salone dell'Alto Artigianato in Venice, VicenzaOro). Among the

reasons for not selling their products, there are the specificities of the product (on-site or tailored made), and the importance of exhibiting their pieces rather than selling them (“I have worked in the eldercare to pay my bills, and exhibited in many ceramic biennials worldwide. And also applied for grants to cover my costs. So it has not been so important to sell, but more important for me to show”), lack of selling skills (“I am not a good salesman”) or time.

Figure 27- Questionnaire results. Where do you sell your products (multiple answers are possible)

It is quite interesting to note that among the platforms (Fig. 28), the most used one is Instagram, a social media that has become the first interaction platform between craft-makers and clients. Only one person indicated Etsy, which instead is a craft-dedicated selling platform. The use of Instagram will be discussed in Section 7.

15 intervistati (60%) hanno risposto **instagram** a questa domanda.

Figure 28 - Questionnaire results. If you use dedicated platforms, which ones are more important?

6.3 Ranking of most important competencies and resources

This section reflects the division in macro-knowledge areas of skills and resources before delineated. Firstly, we asked to rank those macro-knowledge areas: the skills considered most important are the craft-making skills, followed by communication and selling skills, business skills, transversal skills, and finally technological skills (Fig. 29). Concerning resources, the most important are the financial ones, followed by material support (studio, machinery), then the professional network, and lastly the personal network (Fig. 30). So, there is the perception that craft-making skills are the most relevant but they must be paired with financial resources, which is why selling and business skills come just afterwards.

Figure 29 - Questionnaire results. Ranking of skills. “We ask you to rank the following skills and knowledge in order of importance (1 most important - 5 least important)”

Figure 30 - Questionnaire results. Ranking of resources. “We ask you to rank the following resources for the work as a craft-maker, based on your experience, in order of importance (1 most important - 5 least important)”

Secondly, we asked to rank every skill inside the macro knowledge area (from 1 -very useless to 5 - very useful). So, starting from craft-making skills, it can be seen in the graphic below (Fig. 31) that all of the skills are generally considered very important, with making skills/mastery of technique as the most important. Creative thinking and problem-solving are generally considered more important than developing a personal style or research and experimenting (Fig. 31).

42. Rate the importance of each of the following knowledge in the area of craft making skills (1 lower relevance - 5 higher relevance)

Figure 31 - Questionnaire results. Craft-making skills

Technological skills are the set of skills less regarded by craft makers. Indeed, AI interaction and automation are generally considered less relevant, together with 3D printing. There is a more diverse attitude toward the use of technological innovation for researching and experimenting, opening a possibility of collaboration in those phases (Fig. 32).

43. Rate the importance of each of the following knowledge in the area of technological skills (1 lower relevance - 5 higher relevance)

Figure 32 - Questionnaire results. Technological skills

Business skills are also generally considered important, especially project management and time management. There is a more varied perception of the relevance of skills such as entrepreneurship and market analysis, financial and accounting, and leadership. There is a more average perception of the importance of knowing business models and a slightly lower relevance of IP knowledge (Fig. 33).

44. Rate the importance of each of the following knowledge in the area of business skills (1 lower relevance - 5 higher relevance)

Figure 33 - Questionnaire results. Business skills

Communication and selling skills are generally perceived as very important, with marketing and promotion as the most important ones, followed by developing a creative identity and presenting the product. Sales and pricing are also relevant, while social media and e-commerce are considered more of average importance (Fig. 34).

45. Rate the importance of each of the following knowledge in the area of communication and selling skills (1 lower relevance - 5 higher relevance)

■ 1 ■ 2 ■ 3 ■ 4 ■ 5

Figure 34 - Questionnaire results. Communication and selling skills

Finally, transversal skills are considered important but not fundamental as other skills, with a perceived lowest relevance for sustainability and green economy expertise. Cultural awareness and critical thinking are generally perceived as slightly more important than networking skills (Fig. 35).

46. Rate the importance of each of the following knowledge in the area of transversal skills (1 lower relevance - 5 higher relevance)

■ 1 ■ 2 ■ 3 ■ 4 ■ 5

Figure 35 - Questionnaire results

Here it follows a section with a focus on the ranking of the five macro-categories of skills divided by ecosystem (Italy, Sweden, Denmark).

In Italy, craft-making skills are generally considered relevant, with few (2) craft-makers considering artistic sensitivity, personal style and making skills not relevant, or little relevant (1). The most relevant skills are making skills and mastery of craft techniques, together with artistic sensitivity, followed by creative thinking and personal style (Fig. 36).

Figure 36 - Questionnaire results. Italy: craft-making skills

Technological skills are generally considered less important, with AI and 3D printing perceived as the most useless skills by the majority of respondents, followed by automation and robotics (Fig. 37). Research and experimentation with technological tools and digitisation slightly contrast this trend with more average evaluation, and some people consider them important (7) and very important (respectively 10, 7) skills. It seems that the use of technological tools is not yet an integral part of the production process but it can be useful for substituting some phases of the production process (as in the case of digitisation) and in the experimentation phase.

Figure 37 - Questionnaire results. Italy: technological skills

Business skills have a more homogeneous evaluation as important and very important skills, especially project management and time management have the highest ranking (Fig. 38). After that, financial accounting and leadership and human resources are equally relevant competencies, followed by entrepreneurship and market analysis. The less relevant among these skills, are business planning and IP knowledge.

Figure 38 - Questionnaire results. Italy: business skills

Marketing and communication skills are considered even more important than business skills by the majority of Italian craft-makers (Fig. 39). Indeed, these skills collect higher evaluations as very relevant, especially marketing and promotion skills. Sales and client management, and creative identity and the ability to communicate their products follow immediately after. Pricing is also a relevant competence, while the competent use of social media gains equally very high and average evaluations.

Figure 39 - Questionnaire results. Italy: marketing & communication skills

Finally, transversal skills in Italy are considered as important, with critical thinking as the most important skill (Fig. 40). Having a broad knowledge and cultural awareness is more important than networking, and sustainability is considered less relevant. Just one person finds all of these skills as not relevant at all.

Figure 40 - Questionnaire results. Italy: transversal skills

In Sweden craft-making skills are also considered relevant, with creative thinking and problem-solving as the most important, followed by research and experimenting, and mastery of the techniques (Fig. 41). Artistic sensitivity and personal style come right after, with more average evaluations (respectively 5, 4). It reflects more or less the Italian ranking, with little differences that, however, can be due to the less amount of data available.

Figure 41 - Questionnaire results. Sweden: craft-making skills

Also the ranking of technological skills recalls the Italian one, with AI and 3D printing as the less useful competencies, followed by automation and robotic production (Fig. 42). There are some positive evaluations of research and experimentation with technological tools (6 very important and 5 important) with only one respondent that considers it not useful. Digitisation collects average evaluations with 5 respondents that consider it important, 5 who do not, and 5 who do not have strong opinions on it.

Figure 42 - Questionnaire results. Sweden: technological skills

Differently from Italy, business skills in Sweden collect more average evaluations but are still considered generally relevant (Fig. 43). In particular, project management is the most important skill, followed by entrepreneurial skills, which are considered not relevant by 3 people. Developing a business model is considered important (important 7, very important by only 1 person) but it also collects many average evaluations (5), as is the case also of financial accounting which is considered very important by 2 people, equally important (5) and not important (5), and of average importance (3). Leadership skills collect more average (7) and positive (6) evaluations, while IP legal knowledge is considered mainly of average (9) importance.

Figure 43 - Questionnaire results. Sweden: business skills

Marketing and communication are collectively considered as important, since they did not get any negative evaluation (Fig. 44). Overall, marketing and promotion and the development of a creative identity are the most important skills, with only 1 person evaluating them as of average importance. They are followed equally by the use of social media and pricing skills, while sales skills which include client management and communication are the less important and are almost equally considered of average importance (important and very important 8, average 7). This last result differs greatly from the Italian situation in which sales is among the most relevant set of skills.

Figure 44 - Questionnaire results. Sweden: marketing & communication skills

Finally, transversal skills are also overall important and very important, with no negative evaluations (Fig. 45). The most important one is networking with only one person finding it of average importance, contrary to Italy where networking obtained lower results. It is followed by cultural awareness (very important 7, important 5), and then almost equally important there is critical thinking (very important 6, important 5) and sustainability and circular economy (very important 6, important 4), which also collected more average evaluations.

Figure 45 - Questionnaire results. Sweden: transversal skills

In Denmark, the evaluations of craft-making skills are similar to the Italian ones, with mastery of craft techniques and artistic sensitivity as the most important ones, followed by creative thinking (Fig. 46). Personal style and especially research and experimenting are, instead, considered a bit less important and more average (4). This contrasts also with the Swedish results where research and experimenting were among the most relevant skills. However, all of the skills in this category received only positive results, so it can be said that it is in line with the other ecosystems.

Figure 46 - Questionnaire results. Denmark: craft-making skills

It is also in line with the other ecosystems, in the negative evaluations given to technological skills (Fig. 47). AI, automation and robotics, and 3D printing receive the most negative evaluations with respectively 10, 9 and 7 people considering them very useless, and 2, 3 and 3 people considering them just useless. Also in this ecosystem, as in Italy and Sweden, digitisation and research and experimentation receive less negative evaluations (digitisation: very useless 4, useless 7, average 1, very useful 1) or more equally distributed (research and experimentation: very useful 2, useful 3, average 3, useless 3, very useless 2).

Figure 47 - Questionnaire results. Denmark: technological skills

Business skills received more average evaluations compared to Italian craft-makers (Fig. 48). Indeed, the only relevant skills in this case are financial and accounting skills, while the others are considered as more of average importance. Project management and time management are almost equally important (very useful 5, useful 2) and average (6), whereas in Sweden and in Italy it is considered as mostly important. Leadership and entrepreneurship are more of average importance (leadership 8, entrepreneurship 4), with some negative evaluations too (leadership 1, entrepreneurship 4). The evaluations of knowledge of business models and IP are more distributed, with business models gaining 6 positive evaluations, 5 average, and 2 negative; and IP little considered useful (2), average (4), useless (4), and very useless (3).

Figure 48 - Questionnaire results. Denmark: business skills

Marketing and communication, as in the case of Sweden and Italy, got mainly positive evaluations, with also in this case the competencies of marketing and promotion as the most relevant ones (Fig. 49). Developing a creative identity also gained only positive results (very useful 8, useful 5), followed by the competent use of social media (very useful 8, useful 4, useless 1). Sales skills and pricing come afterwards, with sales skills as mainly useful (very useful 7, useful 4) and only 2 average evaluations; while pricing has 4 average evaluations and one person who does not find it useful. These last lower evaluations reflect the Swedish ones.

Figure 49 . Questionnaire results. Denmark: marketing & communication skills

Finally, among the transversal skills critical thinking, networking and having a cultural awareness are the most relevant ones, as in the Italian ecosystem, with networking and cultural awareness having higher numbers of highest evaluations (cultural awareness 7, networking 5) but also of average evaluations (cultural awareness 5, networking 4). Coherently with the other ecosystems, sustainability and circular economy are the less important competencies of this category, reaching more average results (5).

Figure 50 - Questionnaire results. Denmark: transversal skill

6.4 Training vs outsourcing

This section aims to understand which skills the craft-makers are interested in learning themselves and which others, though recognising their relevance, would prefer to have someone else learn it. This part permits us to understand which skills the craft-makers are more eager to learn based on their effective time and interest.

In the graphic below (Fig. 51), it is very evident and homogeneous the general preference of craft-makers for learning new craft-making skills and techniques themselves (81,9%), since it represents their core activity. The large majority would like to spend time researching and experimenting (78,3%) with the material, new materials, and new techniques. Developing critical thinking in relation to materials (83,1%) is also a perceived important skill that craft-makers would like to personally have. Few people (14,5%) think that developing a personal artistic style is not relevant for their production, while 79,5% think it is and want to learn it.

There is a quite homogeneous lack of interest in technologies such as AI (60,2%), 3D (47%), automation and robotics (57,8%), which either are considered not relevant by the majority of craft-makers, or they would outsource to an external service or person (automatic and robotics 33,7%, AI 25,3%). Especially digitisation and 3D

printing/modelling would be likely to be outsourced to an external service, respectively 41% and 34,9%. The only exception is researching through technological tools which 45,8% of craft-makers would be interested in learning themselves, while 33,7% would outsource it, and 20,5% find it not useful for their job.

Among the business-related skills, time and project management is the most desirable skill for craft-makers to possess themselves (66,3%), whereas knowing business models, entrepreneurship and financial and accounting skills are more likely to be outsourced to other people (respectively 56,6%, 53%, 66,3%). 54,2% of craft-makers are eager to acquire leadership and human resources skills, whereas 21,7% prefer to outsource them and 24,1% do not find them relevant. IP knowledge is more divisive, having both craft-makers who consider it relevant (22,9%) and others who do not (18,1%) or prefer to outsource it (59%). In comparison with craft-making skills which are all considered relevant to be acquired by craft-makers and with technological skills, which, on the contrary, are all felt as not relevant for their job, the business-related skills are generally considered relevant but craft-makers are equally divided between the willingness to learn a new skill and outsource it.

Communication skills (marketing, social media, creative identity, sales and pricing) are generally considered relevant. In particular, 51,8% of craft-makers would like to learn how to develop a creative identity (62,7%), marketing, 68,7% pricing techniques, and 56,6% sales methods. Very few of them find these skills not relevant for their job (respectively: creative identity 1,2%, marketing 4,8%, sales 4,8%, pricing 7,2%) and a good part of craft-maker would find it useful to outsource them (marketing 43,4%, sales 38,6%, pricing 24,1%). Social media are considered relevant (only 1,2% do not find them useful) and 51,8% prefer to learn how to use them by themselves, while the remaining 43,4% prefer to outsource them.

Transversal skills are also generally perceived as relevant, with critical thinking (81,9%) and cultural awareness (78,3%) as the most important transversal competency that a craft-maker needs to acquire by themselves. 68,7% would improve networking, while 19,3% would outsource it and 12% do not think it is useful.

■ I would like to do training and education
 ■ I would like to outsource this task to someone with the relevant skill
■ this competence is not central for my craft

48. For each of the following competencies, we would like you to say whether you would like to do training, would like someone to do it for you, or if this competence is not relevant for your craft:

Figure 51 - Questionnaire results. Learning vs outsourcing skills

6.5 Open questions

The last part of the questionnaire included five open questions that permitted responders to provide their thoughts and feelings in a more open way, if compared to the previous questions. The five questions were the following:

- If you had time and resources, in which areas would you prefer to attend formative courses?
- How have you tried to improve your skills so far?
- If you plan to spend time improving your skills, how do you plan to do it?
- Do you think that technological innovation is useful for your work? How?
- What are the main challenges that a craft-maker has to face regarding the acquisition of new competencies and skills?

The first question aimed to explore the perceived educational gaps among craft-makers, attempting to map which courses they would like to take if not constrained by time and resources. Time and resources, indeed, had already emerged from pilot interviews and will be confirmed by the last of the open-ended questions, to be the main constraints to training activities. The second and third questions delve into the specifics of training and education activities, asking craft-makers if they have

undertaken training so far (and what) and how they plan to pursue training and education in the future. The fourth question explores a very particular theme, that of technological innovation. In this context, it serves to bridge with Work Package 2 of Hephaestus, but also to explore the beliefs of craft-makers in a field that could be relevant for the design of curricula, which will take place later in the project. Indeed, technological innovation is potentially a theme capable of revolutionising the work of craft-makers, not without the risk, however, of being controversial. Finally, the fifth question sought to investigate, more generally, what factors might prevent craft-makers from acquiring new skills, as these are important issues to address if one wishes to design training courses and curricula that are truly of interest to artisans. The next paragraphs present the results of the five questions. Overall, respondents of the questionnaire answered 89% of the questions (78 respondents for 5 questions means 390 answers, and only 43 of these were blank).

6.5.1 If you had time and resources, in which areas would you prefer to attend formative courses?

The first of the open-ended questions asks craft-makers to identify in which areas they would have the greatest interest in receiving training. The open nature of the questions allowed respondents to identify more than one area of interest, so that responses identifying relevant training areas totalled 121. These responses can be categorised into 4 main areas: 1) marketing, sales, and online communication; 2) management; 3) craft-related and technical training; and 4) networking. The first and third areas, related to communication and technical training, garnered the highest number of responses.

Training requests we categorised under marketing cover various areas which, in the words of the craft-makers, are not distinguished but part of an organic discourse. This narrative includes online communication techniques, promotion of their work, marketing, pricing abilities, and also photography to disintermediate the digital communication process. Online communication received 26 mentions, such as: "Successful use of Instagram for encouraging sales and show portfolio/ceramic life"; "Promotion and online sales"; and "Managing social media Best practice in hosting an online shop". However, while it's clear that communication is seen as necessary, it is also not necessarily something craft-makers would prefer to do themselves, if outsourcing is possible: "I'd prefer to spend all my time on developing my technical and artistic skills and let somebody else do the business/ selling part for me. Until this becomes an option for me, I'd like to learn/ improve my writing, photographic and graphical skills as part of being able to communicate/ present my work in a professional way." We shall also highlight that the interest in online communication is not naive, but reflects a sophisticated market awareness, as evidenced by this quote introducing the concept of an "international niche market": "As a fine craftsman with 20 years of experience, I find it very difficult to enter an international niche market where my work

can be valued appropriately. That, I don't think that can be learned at any school. It's a conjugation of social activities, networking, and selling oneself." Within this area, also, specific mentions were given to marketing (6), sales (3) to define appropriate prices for craft-makers' work, and photography (2).

The second major training area is management, which collected 28 mentions. Many themes were categorised under this area, each receiving from one to four mentions: accounting and tax management (e.g., "Financial and accounting skills [to do my own books]"), business strategy (e.g., "Business strategy for long-term financial sustainability as a craftsperson"), client and supplier management, human resource management and leadership, project management, time management (e.g., "Learning from masters of crafts, people who work/have worked in the industry, to learn time management and to be effective in my process"), intellectual property management, funding and financing research, and the ability to balance entrepreneurial growth with the ethos and morals of craft.

The third training area mentioned relates to technical and artisanal training: techniques specific to the craft were mentioned 23 times, from painting to printing techniques, working with glass, tufting, embroidery, material knowledge, to woodworking, to name a few examples. The desire to improve artistic capability and expression through courses, artistic practical work, and artist residencies was mentioned 11 times. It was also mentioned technology applied to craft, viewed by some as a way to accelerate the experimentation process. Some craft-makers, then, cite specific programs for 3D modelling, digitization, and image work. Others would like to know more about design and its history, and art therapy. 3 craft-makers note that for courses to be truly effective, they should have a strong practical component, not just theoretical.

The last area mentioned gathers only 5 citations, but it was considered important because it's the area of networking, invoked as a necessary skill to create a net of craft-makers who can support each other through all phases of the process, even on an international scale.

6.5.2 How have you tried to improve your skills so far?

The second question sought to explore the methods adopted by craft-makers to improve their skills. In recounting how they have worked on themselves through education and training up to this point, craft-makers highlighted four particularly relevant pathways: 1) personal research and experimentation; 2) courses and workshops; 3) the role of expert craft-makers; and 4) networking and travelling.

Regarding the first aspect, many artisans emphasise how they have improved their skills through self-directed work and research, and the continuous repetition of the same: "By working intensively in all kinds of weaving, tapestry, floor loom weaving, tablet weaving, and digital weaving"; "Learning by doing"; "training training"; and "Researching, experiencing, experimenting, critical thinking". The work of autonomous research is carried out both through experimentation and research on techniques and materials, realised through a focus on practices, and through individual study using online resources, listening to podcasts, and reading books.

Clearly, autonomous research is not in contradiction with the second mode of training, which is that of formal courses offered by universities, technical schools, and other institutions ("I have participated in the courses that Makers Island provides to craft-makers on Bornholm"). In the words of a craft-maker, one learns through "Courses and work, work, work". The courses mentioned in the interviews are of various nature: intensive workshops and short courses, but also longer courses ("I did a course in basic accounting (5-6 weeks), a one-day workshop on Instagram and participated in two workshops about sustainable craft businesses"). Both in-person ("in-person workshops, online workshops, and many hours with our accountant to learn our own bookkeeping") and online courses ("online training courses (online ceramics school)"). From the content perspective, the courses cover all the main areas discussed in the previous paragraph: technical courses related to craftsmanship ("By short courses and years of education in metal, textile, and wood-techniques"), management courses ("I have taken up various business training, some aimed at sole traders starting businesses, some aimed at craftspeople", "I am always improving my skills within the craft and also within IT, social media, accounting, business strategy and more") and It-tech courses ("attending courses in design, writing, Photoshop, Instagram, Indesign, glaze chemistry, and more that I don't remember just now"). It's interesting that the area of communication, so relevant among the areas requiring training, is mentioned here only once. Furthermore, courses can also serve to understand which skills a craft-maker can successfully develop personally, and for which, instead, outsourcing remains the best way: "Did a 2x times 5 days course in rhino and laser cutting - and that's simply not enough. But enough time to accept that I need to buy the expertise instead ;)"

The third training mode relates to the role of expert craft-makers from whom one can learn tacit skills by working for them ('study and apprenticeship'), using them as mentors ('I hope to work with a mentor in early 2024 to challenge my own artistic practice'), or conducting research work based on their experience: 'I have interviewed craftspersons and ex-workers of the Swedish ceramic industries Ifö, Gustavsberg, and Rörstrand. I want to preserve the knowledge and craft skills these workers had. Now, these industries are no longer active in Sweden, so the skills and knowledge are really disappearing.'

The last learning mode concerns networking, achieved also by travelling and thus on an international scale. Collaborating with other craft-makers serves, for example, to explore new areas ('At the moment I am part of a network/knowledge sharing initiative about sustainability among ceramicists') and to improve one's technique ('asking friends [even though some are willing to share insights, others aren't or are busy], reaching out the local business centre, etc.'). The idea of creating an international network serves several purposes: to confront people with similar interests and businesses ('Traveling worldwide to meet others with the same interest'), to deepen the study of local techniques and cultures ('Traveling to study native Indian ceramics, and to experience other cultures with deep roots'), to confront similar companies, but in completely different contexts ('visiting realities similar to mine, seeking dialogue with realities similar in completely different sectors'). In this context, visiting fairs and craft exhibitions also become relevant ('visited several fairs and art shows').

6.5.3 If you plan to spend time improving your skills, how do you plan to do it?

The third question aims to investigate the manner in which artisans think of acquiring new techniques and skills in the future. Although it is not a mere repetition of the previous question, since past experience in training and learning could have reoriented the priorities and preferred modes by the artisans, the answers closely mirror those just described. Courses and individual research are the learning methods most mentioned by artisans, with 25 and 24 mentions respectively, followed by travel and networking (10 mentions), and the role of expert craft-makers (4).

Regarding the courses that craft-makers plan to follow, most respondents do not specify which courses they intend to enroll in. Among those who do, however, interesting responses emerge. The mentioned areas are those of courses on artisan techniques ('I plan to join a weekend of workshops in one of my main craft areas of interest') or managerial scope ('Following update courses on product communication and brand publicity'). Often a very practical approach is requested: 'I'd like to find a course where once the skills are shown, these can be put into practice and be followed up and reviewed. If this is the case, I'm very happy to dedicate big chunks of time in order to get it right. Whether it's a full week and follow-ups, or a couple of days a week for a period of time.'

Experimentation and individual research are better detailed by artisans. The basic idea is that practical doing is more useful than following courses: 'In general, I prefer in-person training and practical learning, through doing or being with others' and also 'I experiment a lot, trying to formulate my own clay bodies and learning more about ceramic glazes from old industry documents and books'. This is a continuous research

activity ('I do this every day, the plan is to learn or try something new every single day'), which proceeds by experimentation ('Trial and error + research'), also hybridising one's techniques with technology ('Working with the materials and techniques in new settings and with modern technology. Also to work cross-disciplinary with materials from different traditions and cultures to import the ideas into my craft').

The third mode that craft-makers count on undertaking is networking, which allows 'Sharing with colleagues', and 'Learning from other skilled colleagues'. Moreover, one of the modes several craft-makers would like to exploit is that of artistic residencies to 'Travel and take part in international artist residencies, workshops, symposiums'. Finally, an internship with expert craft-makers is mentioned as a mode of technical ('Internship in a master's weaving workshop would be nice') and artistic training ('I would also like to do an internship with a textile artist' and 'Working alongside artisans and artists within their workshops'). Finally, it is also interesting to point out that two craft-makers explicitly referred to the lack of time and money for improving skills. This theme will become particularly relevant in the answers to the fifth question, and there we will talk about it in more detail.

6.5.4 Do you think that technological innovation is useful for your work? How?

Regarding the fourth question, which seeks to investigate whether technological innovation is useful for the work of craft-makers, and how, the answers span the entire continuum from the most enthusiastic yes to the most firm no, passing through curious and undecided attitudes, and even those who understand technological innovation as something that can help in the craftsman's work, but not in their core competencies. The respondents are nonetheless generally positive towards technological innovation, with 29 yes, 19 no, 10 undecided/curious, and 10 who see positive aspects of technology for ancillary activities.

Among those who believe that technological innovation can be useful for the work of the craft-maker, the main applications mentioned are in the development of projects ("I use 3D software and Siemens logo plc"; "Yes, in many ways, I think VR 3D modeling is a very interesting tool to explore for concept generation and exploration"), in the creative process ("I think it is very interesting to use technology to seek more creativity, innovate in materials and facilitate some aspects in the design of craft pieces"; "Yes, new expressions and ideas"; "Yes, my craft has not been applied within design and modern production and I think it would be very interesting to introduce new ways of working and thinking to see how the traditional skills can be applied in new areas"), in improving processes and technique ("Yes, it has helped me a lot and the digitization of weaving patterns and working on the TC2 jacquard loom has improved my technological skills a lot"; "Yes, as a means to compete in the field of working with wood as a material. From furniture making to sculptural work I believe it would be a

great benefit to me in terms of workflow and precision in making", "Yes, digitizing some manufacturing phases"), in reducing production times ("Yes. Reduction of production times", "I think it's really handy for saving me time"), and in improvements of machinery and tools ("Yes. Using them as new tools for my work", "to improve machinery", "greater use of computers for communication and for process management. Improvements to the facilities", "Material and tools are relevant (working with textiles)"). There are also explicit mentions for artificial intelligence ("Sometimes yes. For example, for the 6 months I use AI to generate my ideas in mind. To see the finished work makes me decide to create or not") and 3D printing ("It is, I utilize 3D printing in my process to create molds for slip casting"). And a craft-maker, who does not seem very convinced, sees technological innovation as inevitable: "Yes, regardless one will have to adapt".

Among those who have a negative stance towards technological innovation, the idea is that technology distances craftsmanship from its essence: "No - it is a distraction and diminishes the value of real craftsmanship". Moreover, technological innovation could impoverish the skills of artisans: "In 20 years I've moved from designing 2D AutoCAD, 3D AutoCAD, SketchUp, and now Rhino. I have used 3-axis CNC mills... etc. Technological innovation in crafts is interesting to relieve a lot of hard labor but on another side prevents craftsmen from mastering the original craft and relying on a machine to do the work. Most machines are designed as an evolution of some specific hand tool. Original hand tools and the mastery of their use implies mastering the material and its plasticity. In my case, wood, a designer or someone relying only on a machine and without mastering hand tools, will never totally understand the material and for that, even with the most technological equipment, this will never be used to its maximum potential".

Those in an intermediate position say they are curious about the use of technology, provided it does not alter the essence of craft, which must remain manual "But I am curious to further test the abilities within 3D modeling and augmented reality. More as a critical approach and to open up new interpretations. The art pieces themselves must be material and made by hand. It's the essence in my craft practice". Or they comment that doing things faster thanks to technology could be a good thing, but it might also not be ("sometimes but not always. it can speed things up - but that is not always a good thing.."). Finally, several of the craft-makers who responded to the questionnaire are favorable to the introduction of technology in their work, but for auxiliary processes ("Absolutely! Technological innovation can fasten certain processes and give more space for experimentation. yes, it's a basic tool for: archives, database, learning & teaching, building vivid communities, creating networks, branding, marketing & sales") and, in particular, for communication ("Partially; my work is predominantly manual so technology can help me in the part that involves promoting my work rather than in the work itself"), customer development ("Increasing the number of customers through the

internet") and networking with other artisans ("Networking with colleagues" and "More collaborations across borders and distance. I am not sure how it will apply to the rest of the work I do").

6.5.5 What are the main challenges that a craft-maker has to face regarding the acquisition of new competencies and skills?

The fifth and final open question asks what the main challenges are that a craft-maker must face to improve their skills and competencies. The overwhelming majority of responses identify the main issue as the lack of time and money, often cited together. Time, because time for training is time taken away from production. And money to pay for training costs, or even to support the lost earnings from time spent improving one's competencies. Some quotes from the responses are quite revealing: "Time and Money. I love what I do...AND I work nearly every waking hour. If I am not physically working, I am planning, problem-solving, designing in my mind. If my work were more valued, I would be able to work less for the income I make, giving me more time to expand my skills!" "Time and money or lack of actually," or "time away from your production and money to pay for it." Financial resources are also a problem for buying the tools needed to improve one's competencies: "Buying all the equipment needed, and finding time to learn the methods and tools." Time and resources are the main obstacle to acquiring new skills, being cited a total of 67 times in the responses to the fifth question. However, there are also two other reasons that make life difficult for craft-makers when they want to improve their skills. The first concerns the difficulty of finding suitable training courses and institutions for training: "It's not easy finding highly skilled teachers of crafts. Most courses are at a very basic level," or also "The lack of specialized craft-maker courses, training programs that understand the trade, the financial, accounting, and all processes in general. Courses/workshops that don't only offer theory but a follow-up, that accompany the maker and give the opportunity to practice it with their own business and provide feedback." Institutions are important not only for the quality of courses they offer but also for the facilities available: "Access to training opportunities. Access to peer support and knowledge exchange. Access to facilities that they may not have within their own practice - eg kilns, laser saws, lathes, etc." And endangering the quality of the courses is the progressive lack of expert craft-makers: "Availability of training & scarcity of master craftsmen" is again indicated as one of the main obstacles to training.

Finally, some of the respondents indicate that one of the obstacles to acquiring new competencies is also the fact that the craft-maker profession is changing, and that technical and artisanal competence is no longer sufficient: "A craft maker needs to be a designer and a manager too, so being good at doing your craft is not enough." In this context, it becomes more difficult to have the time and the way to improve technical

competencies to an adequate level: "Smoothly integrating new skills to the same level of craftsmanship as the main craft" is a challenge. But in the new context, change is inevitable: "Sometimes craft makers have to move from comfort zones too) we have to adapt new visions, new styles to be alive in these fast-living conditions" and do not need "Resistance to change. Resistance to embedded habits. Resistance to modernizing and novelties".

7. CO-CREATION WORKSHOP IN DALSLÅNGED

The co-creation workshop is a moment of research between craft-makers and researchers, with the aim of learning and developing together specific understandings of the craft profession and confronting them in different ecosystems. In particular, this workshop was centred on the discussion of skills and curricula for craft makers.

The co-creation workshop took place on 8th March 2024 at Open Wood in Dals Långed and the research group was formed by 2 researchers from Goteborg University, 1 researcher from Copenhagen Business School and 2 researchers from Tor Vergata University, and 6 craft ambassadors of Dals Långed. The workshop, led by Tor Vergata researchers, had a duration of 90 minutes and was structured around the presentation and discussion of preliminary results of the questionnaire on skills and educational gaps, open questions and a debate. Participants seated around a table in a convivial way and a PowerPoint presentation was used to discuss the results.

Firstly, the participants were asked to present themselves and answer the question “What is craft for you?”, which took around 25 minutes. Different definitions emerged, all tied to the specific practice of each craft-maker: for some craft is a way of life with moral and ethical connotations, for someone else craft is a bodily urge to make and the sense of belonging to a community, another person defined the urge as the artistic practice while the craft is the community. Others shared the “driving force in doing” as a definition of craft, adding also curiosity and joy as integral parts. Collaborating with other craft-makers gives more meaning to the craft activity than having its studio, according to one of the makers; whereas another craft-maker defines craft as the understanding of “how things work and go together”, describing his research in past craft techniques as a way of “touching something in the past” and learn about it. Some of them also highlighted how this kind of conversation is rare in craft activity but vital: intellectualization is often neglected while is integral to the making.

Afterwards, the preliminary results of the survey were presented and craft-makers interacted and commented on the data (30 minutes). Some themes emerged concerning communication and in particular the use of Instagram. Communication skills are not generally taught in school, as photographic skills too, which, though, are considered fundamental for the craft work. Almost everyone agreed on the need to learn photographic skills to better communicate the products on selling platforms, social media, or portfolios. It has been suggested to learn it as DIY or to ask friends to take photographs in exchange for favours or products/services. Asking friends for help or collaboration is a way to overcome the stress of being unable to do everything by themselves, generally shared by craft-makers.

Some criticisms arose on the use of images or videos on Instagram: some argue that there is a risk in taking photos or videos that make craft seen as easy to lower the perceived value and consequently the price of the product; on the contrary, others

reply that videos of the production process can show the complexity of the craft. There is the potential for changing the narrative of craft on social media. A craft-maker also pointed out that there is an ambiguous relationship between creating an object and posting it on Instagram: the urge to post can influence your production both in terms of *what* you produce and *why* you produce it.

Instagram is said to be fundamental for the business but a craft-maker warns about followers: a huge number of followers does not translate into sales and clients, indeed generally craft-makers follow other craft-makers using the same material to learn and keep updated. So, followers include both clients and a community of peer craft-makers. Another craft-maker especially highlights the community-building use of Instagram: social media is used to create connections among the same community rather than selling, even though learning how to use it to sell and enlarge your community is a must for business. Facebook has been mentioned for older generations of users and to sell to clients that rely on it more than Instagram.

The questionnaire's part on outsourcing vs learning new skills opened up a debate on which skills can be outsourced to "take stress away" from themselves. Before reaching a selection of skills, however, the craft-makers concluded that money is needed to externalise any activity or to acquire skills. Money is needed to pay people to do your taxes, to take photographs, to attend courses. However, when asked "if they had money would they learn accounting?", the majority of them answered "no". So, it seems that maybe craft-making as a profession is more about being attracted to a material rather than being independent in every aspect of the business. Since one of the characteristics and definitions of craft is all-roundness (i.e. the ability to know and produce every step of the production process) it is interesting to see that it applies only to the mastery of the technique and not to other aspects of the business that could lead to the independence of the professional.

Someone asked if a gallerist could help the craft-maker in the selling, accounting and communication parts of their business but the craft-makers pointed out that the gallery system "is a Stockholm thing" that cannot be found in the rural areas. Moreover, to interact with a gallery the craft-maker first needs to have a portfolio of works as reference, which means that time and resources are needed to produce them beforehand.

In the last part of the workshop, the craft-makers were asked to remember a moment in their career when they felt special for having a skill or ability that was considered relevant and a moment when they felt inadequate because they lacked a skill. They were given 5 minutes to individually think and then the sharing moment lasted 30 minutes. Among the positive moments when they felt special, there is "getting paid" or receiving a salary for a residency, which means being considered valuable by someone. Sharing the same knowledge or ideas in a community of peers and organising workshops that empower people were also mentioned as special moments. Then, they listed a series of skills more than moments and among them there is the

ability to focus on a single task, teaching, doing research in an academic field in addition to carrying on manual work, and playing musical instruments. Among the moments or the lack of skills which make them feel inadequate, there is the lack of competence with CAD/Photoshop programs and with business-related skills, filing taxes, and specific techniques of craft-making. Also teaching was mentioned in a double way: on the one hand, it is perceived as difficult to teach craft to craft-makers more talented than them; on the other hand, there are the insecurities of not being good enough or competent enough in their craft practice while teaching at beginners courses (i.e. imposter syndrome).

This last part highlights personal insecurities which however seem to be rather structural, such as the lack of recognition of craft-makers' value and lack of visibility. Also, the lack of business skills and of photographic and programming skills seems to be structural as absent in craft education and curricula.

Figure 52 - Tools in Open Wood, Dals Långed

Generally, the answers to the questionnaire were in line with the point of view of the Swedish ambassadors. As in the case of Italian craft-makers a different attitude toward social media and online communication can be associated with a generational aspect: the older generation of craft-makers have more difficulties in learning and spending time on social media, even if this could lead to a better visibility or an increase in clients, whereas younger generations of craft-makers can easily learn how to use social media, how to create a website and an e-commerce platform. Also, another common trait is the general lack of acknowledgement of the relevance of craft-maker as a profession and of the value of craft-making as a productive activity, both for the community and for the artistic value in itself.

Differently from Italian craft-makers whose main objective is to sell their pieces, the Swedish ones seem to value the exhibiting part of their production. Some of them are not even interested in selling their pieces, both because of the object's characteristics (e.g. too big to fit in an indoor space, etc.) and because of their artistic attitude. Indeed, the main difference, which is also reflected in the different educational paths, is the idea of the craft-maker as a profession: the Italian ones are structured in a more commercial way (e.g. they have a shop, they identify the selling of their objects as integral in their activity, they offer courses to amateurs to sustain their craft production, etc.), while the Swedish ones are more interested in being perceived as artists (e.g. more attention on the exhibitions, they sometimes curate craft exhibitions, etc.). Reflectively, educational paths follow this differentiation as the majority of Italian craft-makers have a high school level of education, whereas Swedish and Danish ones have a university or postgraduate level of education. The definitions of "designer" and "artigiano" partly reflect this slightly different identity: a more design and artistic one with an emphasis on the theoretical and ethical aspects of craft making, and a more hand-based maker with an emphasis on the mastery of technical skills. The only Italian craft-makers who shared the more artistic/design vision of craft and of craft-maker are those that either have a university degree or have studied abroad in art schools.

Figure 53 - Open Wood, Dals Långed

8. DISCUSSION

From the data presented in the interviews, in the questionnaire, and in the co-creation workshop, different professions of a craft-maker emerged, all sharing a hand based production:

- (a) The **artisan craft-maker**. This figure generally has a shop and a studio and produces functional or decorative objects mainly to sell. Generally, this figure works alone or with other few collaborators, usually part of the family. The clients are people with a passion for artisanal products but also generic people who find his/her products in local markets and are not familiar with craft productions. This is generally a problem because the craft-maker needs to justify high prices for the products which, at a first sight, are not perceived as that much expensive. Moreover, not having a solid base of clients does not guarantee stability in his/her production, which is why this figure needs to have other jobs in order to sustain his/her craft activity.
- (b) The **artist craft-maker**. This figure is more similar to an artist as for positioning, indeed the artist craft-maker does not sell to the general public nor usually attends local markets. His/her main clients are usually public actors such as municipalities of cultural institutions, or universities and art schools, for which he/she produces pieces to be exhibited or to be included in a civic or museum collection. So, the main market is the art market, populated by galleries, institutions, museums, and institutions. The precarity of the commissions, however, forces this figure to carry out multiple jobs to sustain the craft activity. He/she works usually alone or is part of an artistic-craft community
- (c) The **craft company/enterprise**. It is specific to the Italian context, it is between a small-medium enterprise and an individual craft-maker who produces his products by hand. This company is of small-medium size, it generally hires craft-makers to produce its products in a handcrafted manner. However, it can include some mechanisation or automation phases or innovate production processes, while keeping a large part of it dependent on the craft-maker. Indeed, this company is not afraid of technological innovation and it uses it to continue artisanal production or overcome craft sector problems. For instance, a glass production company in order to overcome the inability to do specific manufacturing in glassblowing - lost as the craft-maker who knew them died - it re-invented and re-used a technique, named “casting”, to have the same finished result following a different production process.

The characteristics of these different figures are summarised in Table 2.

Table 3 - A classification of craft-makers

	Artisan craft-maker	Artist craft-maker	Craft company
Object of production	Functional and decorative objects	Unique pieces, artworks	Functional production, sometimes artistic commissions
Quantity	Limited series	One piece, tailor-made	Limited series and unique pieces
Business dimension	Small	One person/Individual	Small to medium
Aim	Selling	Self-expression and exhibiting	Selling
Innovation	Partial. Innovation when the product requires it, mainly traditional production	Artistic experimentation	Technological innovation driven by optimization of production processes
Economic sustainability	No, usually they have other jobs.	No, they have other jobs.	Yes.

These typologies of craft professions have similar skills and skill gaps, as highlighted in the previous sections. For instance, they all agree that technical mastery is not sufficient to be a craft-maker and they generally recognize their lack in business and communication skills. However, according to their typology, they may have different needs in terms of new skills acquisition.

An artisan craft-maker needs more client management and promotional skills than an artist craft-maker, who conversely needs more fundraising skills in terms of applying for artistic funds, grants and artistic residencies. Also concerning communication, the channels, and the “tone” may vary from artisan craft-makers, who may want to stress the handmade aspect, and the artist craft-maker, who instead may prefer to use a more artsy and conceptual language. As for channels of communication, the artist craft-maker may not want to sell directly but prefer intermediation (like a gallery or a school), while the artisan craft-maker sells directly, so it makes sense for him/her to have an e-commerce platform and participate in craft fairs. We think that all craft-makers, even

those who do not sell their products, should be acquainted with pricing and budgeting skills, since they are fundamental also for filling applications for residencies or artistic programmes.

Concerning the skills to be learnt by the craft company, usually they reside in the ability to translate contemporary languages in their craft productions, such as engaging with external designers to bring innovation, or developing new machinery or techniques to overcome production processes and difficulties.

Then, there are competencies that craft-makers know to be essential but would prefer to outsource rather than learn themselves. Among these are accounting, financial advisory, legal support, sustainability, and finding funding opportunities. Some possible solutions to outsource these competencies, since the craft-makers expressed their lack of time but also of interest in learning these, can be the development of a platform or an incubator that provides these accounting/legal and communication services especially tailor-made for the craft sector. Professional figures, such as the manager or communication strategist can also be useful in this context, acting as the mediator who takes care of the more practical and promotional aspects of the craft-maker activity. These figures could also work with multiple craft-makers, similar to communication agencies with multiple clients.

Other skills, such as social media, photography or marketing could also be learnt, especially by younger generation craft-makers, through specific courses, which should be economically accessible. They could be provided by universities or art schools in “non-working hours” or could be available online, so that craft-makers with additional jobs can follow them. These courses can be done by professors but also by professionals, or successful craft-makers that can share their experience.

Finally, all craft-makers argue that making skills must be acquired by themselves and cannot be outsourced, so craft-makers need to have the resources to sustain their life-long learning process. For this reason, artistic grants and craft funding should be available, as well as artistic residencies and collaborations with international peers. An international network should be created with funding resources, maybe coming from European institutions, to effectively sustain this sector. The network should also include universities and cultural institutions to provide visiting periods of study and exhibiting opportunities.

The difficult relationship with technological tools (AI, 3D, automation) can partly be understood as the inability to foresee possible applications in the craft sector on behalf of craft-maker who are not used to using them. However, we believe that especially in the simulation and experimentation phases they can offer interesting solutions.

9. CONCLUSION

We started the research on the skills and perceived educational gaps of craft-makers with a literature review, followed by a series of interviews in Bassano del Grappa and Venice. From these preliminary results and collective sense-making we formulated a categorisation of craft skills in five macro-areas: making skills, technological skills, business skills, communication and selling skills, and transversal skills. We adopted this skills categorisation to develop the questionnaire that we distributed to craft-makers in Europe. Moreover, we presented the results of the questionnaire in a co-creation workshop with the craft ambassadors of Dals Långed, which resulted in a collective discussion on craft skills and curricula and a moment of results' validation. Concerning the perceived missing skills in craft education, craft-makers are aware that they generally lack business-related skills and communication and selling skills, which are considered as very relevant for their production. There are some skills that craft-makers are eager to learn by themselves, especially new craft techniques and making skills, whereas there are other skills which they would prefer to outsource, like accounting, financial skills, finding grants, legal advisory, digital communication, selling and client management. These outsourceable skills can offer new business opportunities for communication and business specialists, who can develop methodologies and platforms dedicated to craft services or can provide consultancy or a mediation activity to craft-makers. Schools and universities can also be involved in offering specific courses on these skills (i.e. marketing and pricing, photography, social media management). From the questionnaire results, technological skills are considered less appealing and important than the others. However, in the interviews and in the co-creation workshop it emerged that some craft-makers consider them as potentially interesting for some specific phases of their production, not as substituting their abilities but as a support for the experimentation or simulation phase. Still, it emerged that craft-makers have little knowledge about these. This does not mean that training in technological fields is irrelevant for craft-makers. On the contrary, the fact that it is not perceived as an educational gap by craft-makers means that technological training cannot start from technical and practical training regarding specific applications, but rather from the analysis of whether and why technology can be useful to an artisan. This, evidently, cannot ignore the specific sectors and materials with which each craft-maker deals. In other words, we cannot take for granted the interest in technological applications, but neither can we say that disinterest stems from a deep understanding of how technology could assist in artisanal work.

These results pave the way for the following tasks within Work Package 4 of Hepheastus “Innovative training curricula for tradition craft-makers of the future”. Specifically, D4.3 will be a “A new life-long learning methodology for craft-makers”,

which will be tested in the following tasks, leading to D4.3 “A report on innovative curricula and their modules”.

The research identified three main typologies of craft-makers: the artisan craft-maker, the artist craft-maker, and the craft company. The first is a one-person or very small business where the craft-maker handcraft every product and whose main aim is the selling of the craft production. The second one is generally a single person with an artistic education who produces mainly to exhibit and express him/herself through his/her craft creation. The craft company is a small-medium business where more than one craft-maker is employed to produce a limited series of functional objects. The different concept of craft-maker (artisan or artist) can be partly connected to the different education paths and careers in Italy and in Sweden/Denmark. In Italy, the general lack of a university level education and the workshop-based education in craft-makers reflects the widespread traditional idea of the craft-maker as an only-manual profession that does not need any theoretical reflection, which is also generally one of the reasons why it is not appealing to younger generations. Instead, in Sweden and Denmark, craft-makers study design at a university level or higher so they understand their profession as in-between academic activities and workshops.

We do not consider data collection closed. While we deliver this report, we also plan to keep collecting data as we develop and test the education and training methodology, so to maintain a virtuous cross fertilisation between data collection, data analysis, and application of results. Therefore we plan to update this deliverable twice, at months 24 and 48. Also, we plan to replicate the co-creation workshop in the other ecosystem to collect more data and better compare the ecosystems.

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